

D4.3

**Co-developed iconic overshoot
adaptation scenario narratives and
high-resolution maps**

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D4.3 Co-developed iconic overshoot adaptation scenario narratives and high-resolution maps

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Abstract: In this report, we co-develop adaptation scenario narratives together with local stakeholders for critical areas within four Iconic cities, using high-resolution maps. Adaptation measures are then remodelled to evaluate their effectiveness on the ground.

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Glossary

ABBREVIATION / ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
Overshoot	Exceedance of risk/impact thresholds. Those can be in terms of global mean temperature increase related to the goals of the Paris Agreement or (local) thresholds related to specific impacts or limits of adaptation actions.
Adaptation scenario narrative	A storytelling framework that outlines potential future scenarios for climate adaptation, including measures and implementation strategies, supported by data modelling, research by design and stakeholder coproduction.
Iconic region	Region that is a representative example (“hotspot”) of acknowledged distinctive regional features of climate change vulnerability.
Iconic city	Cities and urban areas in each of the iconic regions addressed in the project, where vulnerability to various climatic risks have increased because of anthropogenic activity.

Executive Summary

This report presents the efforts within the PROVIDE project to co-develop overshoot adaptation scenario narratives and high-resolution maps in its four iconic cities and iconic regions around the world: **Lisbon Metropolitan Area**, Portugal, Iberian Mediterranean; **Islamabad**, Pakistan, Upper Indus Basin; **Bodø**, Norway, Arctic Fennoscandia; and **Nassau**, The Bahamas, Small Island region.

By modelling climate change hazards, impacts and risks, as well as co-developing adaptation priorities and measures together with local stakeholders, this report completes the two previous PROVIDE-reports on [Four review reports on key overshoot adaptation challenges in Iconic Regions and Cities \(D4.1\)](#) and [Four Overshoot Proofing reports \(D4.2\)](#). This final report addresses local stakeholders' concerns and their stated needs to meet current and future expected climate-related challenges. The emphasis is on nature-based and socially sustainable solutions that are cost-effective, technical feasible and socially accepted, and that can help to manage climate risks while increasing local resilience to identified risks.

The overshoot adaptation narrative scenarios presented in this report are co-developed with local stakeholder and tested with a suit of models, including UrbClim, CLIMADA, and Flood4Cast. Thus, climate scientists and modellers have been working closely together with social scientists, adaptation experts, urban planners, and local stakeholders in making the overshoot scenarios policy-relevant as well as improving local adaptation capacity under the three main climate scenarios defined in the PROVIDE project: *1) Current Policies*, *2) Delayed Climate Action*, and *3) 1.5°C – Shifting Pathways*. Essential in this work is that local stakeholders have directly contributed to what is to be modelled and help define local adaptation hotspots for testing adaptation options. This process has been highly appreciated by the involved stakeholders as a positive way to be involved in research as well as getting relevant scientific knowledge to strengthen their local adaptation.

In two of the iconic cities, the focus is on adapting to heat stress and we study three densely urbanised and populated areas, two in the **Lisbon Metropolitan Area** (Almada and Lisbon) and one in **Islamabad** (sector E-11). In these three selected adaptation hotspots we have created high-resolution maps and models at a 1-meter resolution. Additionally, the whole of the Lisbon Metropolitan Area is analysed and modelled at a 100-meters resolution. To adapt to heat stress, key adaptation scenario narratives for Lisbon include the use of unsealing strategies, individual tree planting along avenues and streets, green roofs/facades, the development of green-blue corridors and green riparian zones, and the development of a system of urban forests and parks. In Islamabad, the proposed adaptation scenario narrative for sector E-11 is mainly to incorporate more nature-based solutions. Although there are synergies with existing national climate change and development policies, we find a need to develop context-specific, climate-smart urban plans in more sectors of Islamabad, which must be tailored to the local needs of the communities.

In **Bodø**, the initial focus was on dealing with flooding within the whole urban area of the city. After initial modelling results and consultation with the local stakeholders, we decided to include also an analysis of heat-stress and drought. Thus, the theme of the adaptation scenario narrative includes a more proactive view on sustainable and resilient spatial developments clustered in four themes: Ecology, Economy and transport, Food, and Quality of life. In the iconic city of **Nassau**, the analysis centre on coastal and flood protection against tropical cyclones and adaptation against rising heat-stress levels. Key

adaptation scenario narratives include to establish green avenues and more parks across the city; unseal private gardens, industrial areas and parking lots; build dikes, sea walls and water retention areas; strengthen foundations and dry-/wet-proofing of buildings.

Throughout this project, local research partners in the four iconic cities have continuously discussed the issues of reversibility of impacts, limits to adaptation, critical thresholds, and social acceptance of the proposed adaptation options with local stakeholders. What we have found is that potential overshoot scenarios on the long-time horizons are the most relevant for long-term, local adaptation planning, mainly consisting of infrastructure-based measures in the urban spatial planning in the iconic cities. Moreover, we have developed adaptation scenario narratives, though a combination of research by design, data modelling and storytelling, which help frame potential needs for climate adaptation in urban environments. These narratives illustrate how the implementation of a set of adaptation measures can help tackle local climate challenges in ways that many stakeholders can relate to. Through this work, we strengthen local adaptation practitioners' understanding of the implications of the choices they make today and contribute with knowledge in how to design science-based adaptation plans for urban areas that support long-term effectiveness and avoid risks of maladaptation. By combining insights from climate models with practical urban planning solutions, the PROVIDE project ensures that adaptation measures are both theoretically sound and practically feasible.

We contribute with knowledge on how to strengthen local adaptation plans, but it is important to point out that all the proposed adaptation measures in the four iconic cities require committed investments and political will to be implemented and finalised. Thus, it is essential that both local stakeholders, politicians and the general public are aware of current and future climate change impacts and what adaptation measures can be implemented today to avoid the worst impacts. Moreover, we highlight the necessity of including local stakeholders and many types of knowledges to tackle the specificities of urban challenges and possible local nature-based solutions, and how urban design can both increase resilience and adaptation capacity as well as the overall quality of life.

1. Introduction

This report builds on the work showcased in two previous reports. In the first report, „Four review reports on key overshoot adaptation challenges in Iconic Regions and cities“ (D4.1), we examine the adaptation challenges in four iconic case study regions and cities: 1) Arctic Fennoscandia, with a focus on Bodø, Norway; 2) The Iberian Mediterranean, with a focus on the Lisbon Metropolitan Area, Portugal; 3) The Upper Indus Basin, with a focus on Islamabad, Pakistan; and 4) The Bahamas, with a focus on Nassau. While these four iconic regions are very different, they all experience risks and hazards of climate change impacts, including those related to more frequent and serious severe weather events. In all the cases, these impacts are exacerbated by socio-economic factors. Other common features affecting the adaptation capacity are urbanisation pressures, high degree of private land ownership, and the lack of governance incentives and structures. Moreover, in all four iconic cities, the vulnerabilities to various climatic risks have increased due to human activities such as intensified built-up of urban space and reduction of natural or green spaces in the city.

In the second report, „Four Overshoot Proofing reports“ (D4.2), we presented the results from high-resolution modelling of climate change hazards, impacts, and risks in the four Iconic Cities (IC): (i) air temperature and thermal comfort in the Lisbon Metropolitan Area and Islamabad; (ii) flooding in Bodø; (iii) and cyclones in Nassau. We also showed the results from the application of the PROVIDE overshoot proofing methodology which was co-developed with stakeholders in the four case study locations.

Therefore, in this third report, we build on the mapping of critical areas within the four urban areas from the two previous reports, to enhance their adaptation capacities through the development of adaptation scenario narratives built using high-resolution maps. This work has mainly been carried out by the urban planners in the PROVIDE project together with the modellers and case-responsible partners in the four iconic cities in close collaboration with local stakeholders. This involves the co-development of iconic overshoot adaptation scenario narratives and the creation of high-resolution maps, essential for understanding and addressing specific climate risks and adaptation needs.

Adaptation scenario narratives are frameworks that outline potential future scenarios for climate adaptation in urban environments, as a combination of research by design, data modelling and storytelling. The result is cohesive narratives that illustrate how the implementation of a set of adaptation measures can help to tackle climate challenges in an overshoot scenario, in a way that all types of stakeholders can relate to. In that way, stakeholders can better understand the implications of their choices, and the adaptation scenario narratives foster discussions on effective strategies for building resilient urban communities in a context of extreme climate change.

Urban planning is integral to both developing adaptation scenario narratives and making them useful for the stakeholders working with climate adaptation measures and strategies at the local level. Moreover, an urban planning perspective explores possible adaptation measures within the urban fabric such as enhancing green spaces, optimizing urban layouts for better ventilation or infiltration of surface water, using reflective materials to reduce heat absorption, build natural water runoff sites, and developing infrastructure that can withstand extreme climate events. By combining insights from climate models with practical urban planning solutions, the PROVIDE project ensures that adaptation measures are both theoretically sound and practically feasible. The overall approach is illustrated in **Error! Reference source not found.** below.

Figure 1. General planning and design methodology to address the different hazards and risks faced by the Iconic Regions and Cities. Source: BUUR PoS, 2024

1.1. Spatial measures and policy recommendations for adaptation

Overall, the premise is that when addressing a particular risk, space must be organized to provide corresponding services. The manifestation of the spatial functions is furthered by a series of relevant policy-level recommendations for the implementation of a set of specific spatial measures. Policy recommendations can take the form of generalized strategic guidelines. The combination of adaptation measures, a better insight in the functioning of regulation systems and the translation of those insights into urban planning and design principles, build up the core of strategic spatial planning and the research by design that is carried out in each of the four iconic cities in the PROVIDE project. The understanding of how such planning practices relate to climate risk mitigation and adaptation through the sequence of policy recommendations, functions and services is supported by the digital modelling of the measures using high-resolution maps. We have also evaluated these measures together with local stakeholders in each of the cases.

For example, in the context of heat stress adaptation, policy recommendations can take the form of generalized strategic guidelines to:

- promote soil unsealing, which contributes to reducing heat absorption by hard surfaces and the experience of heat stress around them
- enhance ecological density and surface water, which increases cooling through evapotranspiration
- promote the ventilation of air currents throughout the urbanized landscape, which contributes to decrease the UHI effect
- provide covered spaces, i.e. planting trees, to increase cooling through shading
- strategically cool places and buildings through structural measures such as using cooling materials (that reflect instead of absorb heat), green roofs and/or facades, and architectonic interventions (i.e. window blinds etc.)

The policy recommendations are applied through concrete spatial greening measures implemented in the urban space, for example:

1. create more green avenues and tree-lined streets, and greening private gardens, industrial sites, and car parks, to overall replace traditionally sealed surfaces with vegetation,
2. create urban, peri-urban and regional parks and forests, and agroforestry regimes, which increases the taller vegetation throughout the entire metropolitan areas and around functions that are strongly affected by higher temperatures and heat extremes,
3. green riparian zones and mobility infrastructure verges which contributes to increase green linear elements that traverse urban areas, connect them to their countryside, and promote air ventilation,
4. green squares, playgrounds and transport waiting spots, which provides cooling where people gather and move throughout the day, and
5. use cooling materials and cooled facilities that provides comfortable indoor temperature conditions).

For these and other heat stress adaptation measures, we have created a catalogue that gives an overview of the possible types of interventions, their characteristics and potential impact. Throughout this report, we will use examples from this catalogue as illustrations of adaptation measures. The full catalogue developed by the PROVIDE-partners from BUUR Part of Sweco can be found in Annex 1, page 72 in this report.

Figure 2. Urban forests and Parks as an example of heat-stress adaptation measures Source: BUUR PoS, 2024

1.2. Co-development of adaptation narratives with local stakeholders

The active involvement and co-development with local stakeholders have been essential in our work with the four Iconic regions and cities. Throughout the project, local research teams have conducted several workshops and webinars, informing about the PROVIDE project as well as involving local stakeholders in determining what policies to overshoot proof, what areas of the cities to focus on, and what adaptation measures to explore further. With continuous feedback and collaboration with the local stakeholders and with the guidance and expertise from the urban planners from BUUR Part of Sweco in the project, we have also developed adaptation scenario narratives for the four cities. We have chosen to work differently in the different cases as the varieties in contexts, capacities, and local interests have steered us in different directions. We have accepted the different contexts and the different starting points and needs of the local stakeholders. In all the iconic cities, the stakeholders have mainly consisted of people working directly with local adaptation efforts (e.g. municipal (urban) planners, climate policy advisors, elected politicians) as well as been open to other interested parties (e.g. from the public, businesses, companies, non-governmental organisations).

Because of the different contexts, investigated climate risks and the difference in availability of spatial data, the researchers had to develop a specific approach for each of the four iconic cities. In the Lisbon Metropolitan Area, an extensive data-driven analysis could be carried out, both on local and metropolitan level, in strong collaboration with the local stakeholders. In Islamabad, a lack of specific data led to a much more research by design-based approach, focusing on one specific sector in the city. Here the design proposals, built around concrete adaptation measures, create the framework for an impact evaluation. In Bodø, the adaptation scenario narratives adopt a broader perspective on resilient urban development in coproduction with local stakeholders, due to the absence of clearly identifiable extreme climate hazards. In Nassau, the absence of good spatial data led to a reduced approach, including data modelling and research by design, but in a more scaled-back way.

Photo 1. Second stakeholder meeting in the Lisbon Metropolitan Area on 6 November 2023 © R. E. Coelho

Photo 2. Second stakeholder meeting in Bodø Municipality, 4 June 2024 © H. G. Lindberg

Photo 3. Physical and online stakeholder meetings in Islamabad, 19-20 April 2024 © M. S. Khan

1.3. The utilised modelling tools and platforms

To develop adaptation scenarios and connected narratives, and to assess their effectiveness in future climates, it is crucial to obtain an accurate assessment of the climate risks that the four iconic cities are facing. This also contributes to develop a framework for implementing different overshoot adaptation options to avoid adverse tipping points and allow for future reverse adaptation. Advanced modelling tools and platforms play a crucial role in the process of developing detailed climate risk analysis. We have mainly made use of UrbClim, CLIMADA, and Flood4Cast in this part of the PROVIDE project. In what follows, we provide a short overview of these models. For a more comprehensive description of the modelling tools see report D4.2, section 1.5.

The UrbClim-model simulates spatial resolution climate variables at the scale of a city (De Ridder et al., 2015). It makes it possible to simulate changing climate effects onto detailed land use representations, not only including today's land use but also potential effects of physical adaptation measures. This setup allows us to investigate the effect of large-scale interventions which impact greater areas (as the resolution is limited to 100 meters). In addition, the UrbClim-model and its extension HiREx (Souverijns et al., 2023; based on Liljegren et al. 2008) allow for more detailed analyses, up to a meter-scale, and the identification of, for example, the effect of individual buildings, roads, and trees on the level of heat stress within the city. This makes it possible for us to design detailed adaptation measures, such as the protection or planting of individual trees in the urban fabric, and to assess their effect on urban heat stress. The UrbClim and HiREx extension

are applied for both present and future climates, according to the three main climate scenarios defined in the PROVIDE project. These are scenarios under 1) *Current Policies*, 2) *Delayed Climate Action*, and 3) *1.5°C – Shifting Pathways*.

In addition, we have calculated heat stress, characterized by the **Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT)** which combines temperature, humidity, wind speed, and solar radiation in one metric. This gives an accurate representation of the heat stress that human beings feel when performing outdoor activities (ISO:7243).

Figure 3. Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT) Source: VITO

CLIMADA is an open-source and open-access climate risk modelling and adaptation option appraisal platform (Aznar & Bresch 2019; Bresch et al. 2021) based on IPCC’s definition of risk using hazards, exposures and vulnerability. It works with input data of any spatial and temporal resolution. CLIMADA has been applied for selected impact indicators for present and future climate, without and with adaptation measures, according to the three main climate scenarios defined in PROVIDE as mentioned above. For heat impacts, the outputs at 100-meter resolution from the UrbClim model will be used for the hazard component. For tropical cyclone impacts, the wind field and surge modules in CLIMADA are used together with global sea-level rise estimates from the MAGICC-SLR model. For human impacts the Worldpop 100-meter resolution UN-corrected constrained population count datasets was used. For the asset impacts the LitPop module (Eberenz et al., 2020) was used.

The Flood4Cast model integrates hydrological modelling with water drainage flow models to provide data about potential surface flooding. It is based on commonly available GIS data which facilitates quick model building.

In the chapters that follows we zoom in on each of the iconic cities and the co-development of overshoot adaptation scenario narratives with the use of high-resolution maps. We have ordered the cases according to their climatic risks of heat (Lisbon and Islamabad), floods (Bodø), and hurricanes and sea-level rise (Nassau).

2. Adaptation scenario narratives for Lisbon Metropolitan Area ¹

Photo 4. Lisbon Metropolitan Area, Portugal © getlisbon

Lisbon Metropolitan Area is the most populous area in the country, with 2,871,133 inhabitants (2021 census), composed of 18 municipalities (see Figure 4, next page). Lisbon Metropolitan Area is exposed to a wide range of climatic hazards, in particular extreme heat events and heatwaves. Studies on climatic changes in the Lisbon Metropolitan Area (PMAAC-AML) show a strong trend of increasing frequency and magnitude of the number of heatwave days in the Lisbon Metropolitan Area by 2030. In fact, the bioclimatic projections using RCP 4.5 and 8.5 scenarios for 2041-2070 and 2071-2100 predict increase in maximum, mean and minimum temperatures (between 1.2°C and 3.5°C), increase in thermic gradient coast-inland in summertime and increase in thermic discomfort by heat.

The PROVIDE project has mapped critical areas within Lisbon Metropolitan Area to better enhance its adaptation capabilities under overshoot scenarios (Reports D4.1 and D4.2). Here we present a catalogue of spatial measures to be applied towards an adaptation scenario narrative at two different scales of analysis and policy strategy: one at the whole Lisbon territory, and a second at two selected zoom-in areas of 500x500 meters in the municipalities of Almada and Lisbon.

Co-development of adaptation scenario narratives with local stakeholders was essential in the co-development of the spatial measures to apply at the Lisbon Metropolitan Area. After, a set of policy-level recommendations was designed by the local PROVIDE-team for the implementation of specific adaptation planning measures at the municipality level. At the end, the suggested adaptation narratives were put to practice by re-modelling the region's risk profile and applying a combination of the selected adaptation measures to the entire Lisbon Metropolitan Area and the two selected adaptation hotspots: Almada and Lisbon Municipalities. The results of the climate and impact modelling of the adaptation narratives and the spatial conclusions that can be drawn are important to

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further guide policy, planning and design. Lastly, we discuss the contextual specificity of Lisbon and the particularities it entails for the implementation of the study and its results.

Figure 4. Municipalities in the Lisbon Metropolitan Area

2.1. Adaptation narratives and design measures

In the previous PROVIDE-reports (D4.1 and D4.2), we have mapped the areas within the spatial structure of the Lisbon Metropolitan area that are critical for the adaptation to higher temperatures and the mitigation of the effects of heat stress and urban heat island effects. The project’s overall approach in the case of Lisbon is illustration in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Research, planning and design methodology developed for the elaboration of adaptation narratives of Lisbon Metropolitan Area to higher temperatures, heat stress and associated extremes. Source: BUUR PoS, 2024

To address both current and future risk from heat stress, space must be organized and planned to provide effective heat regulation and cooling services. This means to, for example, ensure more (natural) shading, evapotranspiration, and heat reflection/emission functions. In the list below we describe the spatial measures that were utilized in the planning and design of the IR/IC (the full catalogues of the measures developed for this project to address heat extremes can be found in Annex 1, page 72).

A.1: Green ventilation corridors (vegetated verges): Green ventilation grids are linear green spaces that are strategically located to facilitate the flow of cool air into the city. They are integrated into the urban infrastructure, such as along roads or railways, to provide a cooling effect.

A.2: Areas of ecological value (ecosystem restoration): Creating areas of ecological value and ecosystem protection and restoration are nature-based solutions for urban cooling that help to reduce the urban heat island effect and provide additional benefits such as improved air quality and increased biodiversity.

A.3: Green-riparian zones (ecological corridors): Green-riparian zones and ecological corridors are nature-based solutions for urban cooling that involve creating green spaces along waterways and other natural features in the urban environment.

A.4: Urban forests and Parks: Forests and parks are nature-based solutions for urban cooling that involve the strategic planting and maintenance of mixed forests with open areas that meet various social demands and can also produce biomass.

A.5: Green avenues and tree-lined streets: Green avenues are nature-based solutions for urban cooling that involve the creation of linear green spaces that are aligned with the direction of prevailing winds to facilitate the flow of cool air into the city.

A.6: Green squares and playgrounds: Green squares and playgrounds are nature-based solutions for urban cooling that involve the creation of green spaces within the urban environment, which provide refugia for wildlife, recreational and cultural programs, and amenities or urban communities.

A.7: Green roofs and facades: Green roofs and facades can help mitigate the urban heat island effect by providing shading and evapotranspiration. They are vegetated structures that consist of a waterproofing layer, growing medium, and vegetation.

A.9: Private Gardens: Non-public areas such as private gardens greatly influence the urban micro-climate and the perceived temperature. They can help mitigate the urban heat island effect by providing shading and evapotranspiration, as well as by reducing the number of impervious surfaces in urban areas.

A.10: Green industrial sites: Heavily sealed areas like industrial sites greatly influence the urban micro-climate, the perceived temperature, and the control of the water mission.

A.11: Green car parks: Car parks that see less intensive use can be paved with surfacing open to vegetation and be planted with trees. These car parks can serve as cool islands in the town or city. industrial estates, harbours and business estates are some of the hottest urban areas.

A.12: Individual trees: Trees are the most effective cooling measure because they not only provide shade but also help cool the air through evaporation.

A.13: Soil unsealing (planted/permeable surfaces, lawns): Removing paving creates more room for plantings and the plants keep the area cooler on hot summer days. It also offers animals, plants and soil life more space.

The spatial measures in the mentioned list occur in specific spaces, so-called “regulation systems”, which correspond to the system of open spaces (urban, ecological/surface water-related and infrastructural) that can host them. For the regulation systems to fulfil their promise, they need to be structured according to particular principles:

- 1) they need to be coherent with the conditions of the ground, as e.g. topography affects surface temperature levels,
- 2) they need to permeate the urbanized landscape, as e.g. enclosure of sealed surfaces minimizes the effects of possible ventilation of air currents,
- 3) they need to be porous, as e.g. the provision of cool spaces should follow the everyday movement patterns of the population,
- 4) they need to be flexible, as e.g. the sealing of the ground with hard surfaces and the use of non-cool materials limits the potential of cooling,
- 5) they need to be contingent with overall adaptation strategies, as e.g. they need to target strategic and tactical locations of emergency and daily activities.

The evaluation of the performance of the individual measures and their impact is discussed later in section 2.2.2, where the aforementioned principles are also interrogated resulting in a series of general spatial planning and design guidelines.

Figure 6. Green car parks as heat adaptation measure, example from the measures catalogue in Annex 1. Source: BUUR PoS, 2024

Three adaptation policy recommendations based on the spatial and design measures against heat stress as mentioned above (also see Annex 1, page 72) were proposed for the overall Lisbon Metropolitan Area:

1. Soil unsealing of urbanized and infrastructural areas, through an average increase of 20% of the non-paved area of urban and mobility infrastructure surfaces, and their replacement with low vegetation (Figure 7a).

2. Strategic increase in high vegetation (woodland) in:

- all nationally designated “ecological corridors” (areas for the protection areas of ecological value, species migration and conservation of riparian zones) by wooded cover. Existing vegetation is substituted with wooded cover, to evaluate the potential of the ecological corridors to act as cooling infrastructure for Lisbon Metropolitan Area (Figure 7b);
- infuse open spaces within a buffer of 822 m and 117 m around higher hierarchical roads (motorways and primary roads respectively) with trees, to investigate the utilization of the transport axes that permeate both the urban areas and the whole metropolitan area as ventilation infrastructure (Figure 7c); and
- any additional and accessible open spaces and parks along the same mobility infrastructure axes, to provide both a regional system of urban forests and parks in peri-urban and extra-urban areas to act as cool spots, as well as to strengthen the system of a green-grid further than merely linear green elements and towards linear interconnected green patches and, thus, increase air ventilation (Figure 7d).

3. Increase in the tree cover of areas of agricultural production that lie on flat terrain and the promotion of agroforestry regimes, especially in cases where crops are exposed to higher temperatures due to local geomorphology (Figure 7e).

Figure 7a-e. Individual spatial strategies and measures composing the overall adaptation narrative of the Lisbon Metropolitan Area against higher temperatures, heat stress and associated extremes. Source: BUUR PoS, 2024

The combination of all the adaptation policy recommendations for Lisbon Metropolitan Area is presented in Figure 8 (next page).

Figure 8. Cumulative adaptation narrative of the Lisbon Metropolitan Area against higher temperatures, heat stress and associated extremes. Source: BUUR PoS, 2024

2.1.1. Selected adaptation hotspots: Almada and Lisbon

In the Lisbon Metropolitan area, two hotspots were selected in the two municipalities. The first selected hotspot is in the Almada area; a dense, historical urban area of the city where housing, services, education and extremely high levels of mobility are important features. The adaptation strategy developed for this hotspot consists of a generalized soil unsealing strategy with a tactical implementation of cool spaces whenever possible, while individual trees complete the picture. In specific, the strategy includes (Figure 9):

- **Unsealing** paved surfaces currently utilized as car parks or squares, using permeable materials with low vegetation, complemented with the use of individual broad leaf trees when possible/feasible.
- **Greening** used as a general tactical strategy - rather than structural due to the specificity of the built environment - by increasing both high (trees) and low vegetation (grassland), where it seems feasible to be done, while ensuring connectivity whenever possible.
- **Cooling spots** promotion (populated by high vegetation) in public (urban forests/parks), semi-private (internal block courtyards) and private areas (private gardens). In the hotspot area, these are bounded together by two axes (West-East, Av. Dom Nuno Álvares Pereira - Av. Dom Afonso Henriques) and (North-South, including Rua Cândido Capilé – Praça São João Batista) using additional individual tree planting.

Figure 9. High-resolution map of the adaptation plan for a selected adaptation hotspot in Almada Municipality against higher temperatures, heat stress and associated extremes, together with an aerial view of the current situation, a schematic diagram of the logic behind the strategy and an illustrative section. Source: BUUR PoS, 2024

Figure 10. Illustrative section (in two parts) of the selected adaptation hotspot in Almada Municipality showing the spatial organization and relations between the different heat regulation measures and their embeddedness within the urban fabric. Source: BUUR PoS, 2024

The second selected hotspot in Lisbon lies in a low-density urban area of the city. Former social housing projects are the predominantly urban feature in the area, with additional services, education and sporting elements, and with a very pronounced mobility axis (railway) dividing the area from West to East. The adaptation strategy developed attains a more structural character, consisting of an (almost) contiguous structure of peri-urban forest/park framing that envelops the current and future urban developments. In specific, the strategy includes (Figure 11, next page):

- **Greening** as a structural function, by allocating high vegetation (trees) in wider spaces spanning existing and planned corridors, such as roads and railways, going north-south and west-east, essentially, enveloping the current and future urban developments.
- **Infusing the urban tissue** (both current and planned) with individual trees, cool spots and unsealed surfaces on paved areas currently dedicated to cars, urban squares or internal urban block/building courtyards.
- **Tactically design cooler spots** using broad leaf trees wherever possible.

Figure 11. Adaptation plan of a selected hotspot in Lisbon Municipality against higher temperatures, heat stress and associated extremes, together with an aerial view of the current situation and a schematic diagram of the logic behind the strategy. Source: BUUR PoS, 2024

2.2. Evaluation of the adaptation measures

2.2.1. Modelling of adaptation options

The main goal of the adaptation measures from a climatological perspective is to reduce heat stress within the city. Therefore, we will assess the effectiveness of the different adaptation scenarios outlined above on temperatures and the number of days per year with heat stress in the Lisbon Metropolitan Area (Figure 12).

Figure 12 Number of days with heat stress over the Lisbon Metropolitan Area with present land use and climate (2001-2020). A satellite image (from Google Earth) of the same area is added to facilitate interpretations. Source: VITO

Currently, heat stress occurrence is distributed highly uneven over the Lisbon Metropolitan Area. Coastal areas in the western part of the domain benefit from cooler sea breezes, while areas with trees/forests also provide significant cooling compared to their surroundings. More inland areas attain the highest heat stress levels, with up to 50 days per year with heat stress for the inland locations. These are generally areas with limited amounts of (high) vegetation and that are directly impacted by high amounts of solar radiation and limited options for shade. Urban areas also pop up being hot spots, but also here some discrepancies within the city can be observed, depending on the amount of concrete, open space (leading to higher heat stress levels) or shade and vegetation (leading to lower heat stress levels).

For the five adaptation scenario narratives outlined above, the impact on maximum temperatures, minimum temperatures and heat stress is calculated.

With respect to maximum temperatures, trees have a tempering effect on maximum temperatures. This is reflected in Figure 13 below, where we can see that trees lead to a lowering of the daily maximum temperature of approximately 0.3-0.5°C, depending on their location and compactness. In contrast, unsealing has a marginal effect on daytime temperatures, mainly because in the simulations here, the sealed surface is replaced by low vegetation.

Figure 13. Yearly maximum average temperature for the Lisbon Metropolitan Area at present-day (2001-2020) with a) present land use b) Park system spatial strategy c) the difference between both with respect to temperature. Source: VITO

Nighttime temperatures are heavily influenced by the urban heat island effect, leading to higher temperatures in areas with high urbanization. This is reflected in Figure 14a, highlighting the city as a hot spot for nighttime temperatures. Unsealing the surface leads to less concrete and impervious surfaces, which will store less heat during the day, and therefore also release less heat during the night. Unsealing is therefore a very good strategy to lower nighttime temperatures, leading to temperature decrease of 0.5°C or more in urban areas. Trees on the other hand, have a warming effect during the night, certainly when planted on previously open areas. Their canopy efficiently stores daytime temperatures and prevents radiative cooling (Beele et al., 2024). This feature must be considered in adaptation planning.

Figure 14. Yearly minimum average temperature for the Lisbon Metropolitan Area at present-day (2001-2020) with a) present land use b) soil unsealing spatial strategy c) the difference between both with respect to temperature. Source: VITO

Considering the combined heat stress metric, i.e. the number of days with heat stress (a combination of temperature, humidity and radiation), the positive benefits of the spatial strategies outlined above become even more clear. Trees offer the greatest benefits of lowering heat stress, by providing shade and lowering temperatures. Areas that are currently open spaces benefit most from the presence of trees, lowering the amount of heat stress days in some regions by 50% (Figure 15). Despite a lower magnitude, soil unsealing also lowers the amount of heat stress days. The lower number of concrete / sealed surfaces leads to lower radiation uptake for example. A reduction of 20% in the number of heat stress days can be achieved within city limits by unsealing (Figure 15, next page).

Figure 15. Yearly number of days with heat stress for the Lisbon Metropolitan Area at present-day (2001-2020) with a) present land-use b) park system spatial strategy c) the difference between both with respect to the number of days. Source: VITO

Figure 16. Yearly number of days with heat stress for the Lisbon Metropolitan Area at present-day (2001-2020) with a) present land-use b) soil unsealing spatial strategy c) the difference between both with respect to the number of days. Source: VITO

Apart of large-scale adaptation modelling, also the impact of the detailed spatial design of the municipalities of Almada and Lisbon on heat stress amounts are analysed with the HiREx model, which allows meter-scale detailed heat stress discrimination. One typical hot day in summer 2020 has been selected to showcase the heat stress pattern for present-day land use and the proposed land use adaptation strategies (

Figure 17).

During this hot summer day, both areas in Lisbon and Almada experience very high levels of heat stress in open areas, regardless of their land use (

Figure 17a and c). People who are affected by direct sunlight are therefore already at present-day very susceptible to heat risks. The only places where lower heat stress values are achieved are in the shade of trees and buildings. Moderate heat stress is usually achieved under trees in Almada, while for building shade, high heat stress levels are usually found.

With the adaptation modelling considered (

Figure 17b and d), the areas in which moderate or high heat stress are encountered are much more abundant. This offers the population more options to find shielding to the very high heat stress levels. In Almada, the higher abundance of trees showcases the efficiency of grouping the trees, as lowest heat stress levels are found when tree crowns are connected.

Figure 17. Heat stress simulation for a summer day at present climate for the adaptation hotspots in Lisbon (a and b) and Almada (c and d) for present-day land use (a and c) and proposed land use (b and d). Numbers in black dots represent heat stress categories using WBGT (legend). Source: VITO

2.2.2. Impact of adaptation options

Towards the future, we see an increase in heat stress levels in all scenarios. For the *Current Policies*-scenario by the end of the century, we visualized the heat stress levels in the land use adaptation scenario (Figure 18 b and d). Even with adaptation, most areas that are not shielded from direct sunlight will reach levels of extreme heat stress. Also trees and

building shade will become less effective in mitigating heat stress. High heat stress levels are achieved under trees, while other shade attains very high heat stress levels. This shows that cooling options will be heavily impacted by climate change in the future and will reduce their effectiveness in future reverse adaptation (compare Figure 17 and 18).

Figure 18. Heat stress simulation for a summer day in a future climate (Current Policies by the end of the century) for the adaptation hotspots in Lisbon (a and b) and Almada (c and d) for present-day land use (a and c) and proposed land use (b and d). Numbers in black dots represent heat stress categories using WBGT (legend). Source: VITO

For the five adaptation options modelled in section 2.2 for which daily maximal temperature, daily minimal temperatures, and heat stress days were discussed in the section 2.3.1, the change in impact on people was assessed for the current climate and future pathways (Current policies, Shifting pathways and Delayed action). The population density distribution is considered static as in 2020. The highest heatwave warning level for the Lisbon Metropolitan Area based on the maximal daily temperatures is used to determine the number of people affected by extreme daily heat. The empirical sleep-loss function of minimal temperature derived by Minor et al. (2022) is used to determine the cumulative long-term health impact of lack of sleep. For details on the methodology see PROVIDE-report D4.2. As shown in Figure 19 below, the adaptation options reduce the daily and nightly heat impacts on people to varying degrees.

Figure 19. Change in heat impacts on people (orange) for heatwave warnings (a), extreme heat stress (b) and loss of sleep (c) along the delayed action overshoot pathway (at global temperature overshoot peak in 2061-2070 and end of century 2091-2100) and the effect of unsealing (green) and ecological corridor (purple) cumulated for the whole Lisbon Metropolitan Area.

Under the delayed climate action overshoot pathway, the unsealing and park system adaptation yield contrasting effects during the day and the night. While unsealing can offset most of the increase in impacts from climate change for the reduction in sleep, it overall increases the number of people affected by daily maximum heat. This is because unsealing mostly reduces radiation, and thus is useful in decreasing heat stress (wet bulb globe temperature). However, maximum temperatures might increase slightly due to a decrease in terrain roughness, and thus lead to an increase in people warning days. For more details on the underlying mechanism see section 2.3.1. The park system contributes to reducing daily maximum temperatures, but only slightly reduces the impact on people, as trees can mostly be planted in low population density areas. Furthermore, trees can store heat from the day preventing temperatures from decreasing at night. Overall, however, the reduction in sleep loss is negligible (within the UrbClim model uncertainty).

Figure 20. Change in heat impacts on people for heatwave warnings (a), extreme heat stress (b) and loss of sleep (c) along the delayed action overshoot pathway (at global temperature overshoot peak in 2061-2070 and end of century 2091-2100) with unsealing (top) and park system (bottom) for each location in the Lisbon Metropolitan Area with a population of at least 5 people per 100m². Note that changes below 1% are considered within the uncertainty of the UrbClim model. Source: VITO

The picture becomes more differentiated when looking at the impact at each location as shown in Figure 20. Unsealing reduces strongly heat stress in urban areas, and sleep loss in the whole region. The park system strongly reduces heat stress overall and helps with heat warnings in the more urban areas.

2.3. Implementation strategies and next steps

The Lisbon metropolitan plan for adaptation (PMAAC-AML) prospects the application of spatial planning measures for the mitigation of climate risk at the Lisbon Metropolitan Area and the municipality scales, based on four strategic objectives (OE). The individual measures and general recommendations proposed in our work are closely related to several adaptation strategies proposed by the PMAAC-AML (Table 1).

Table 1. Correspondence between strategic objectives from the Lisbon metropolitan plan for adaptation (PMAAC-AML) and the adaptation measures proposed by the PROVIDE project.

Strategic objectives in the Lisbon metropolitan plan for adaptation	Adaptation measures proposed by the PROVIDE-team ²
(OE1) Mitigate the impacts of rising temperatures in the agroforestry potential, by using forestry mosaic spatial planning	Increase the presence of trees within agricultural land uses. Combine trees and crops in flat agricultural terrains. (Measure C1)
(OE3) Mitigate the impact of heatwaves on human health by reducing the exposure to heat	Eliminate structures/materials that increase heat accumulation or add vegetation that allows tactical cooling spots (e.g., urban forests/parks, green squares), which can significantly decrease the exposure of population to heat. (Measures A4 to A7)
(OE4) Reduce the impacts of rising temperatures in infrastructures by reducing the exposure and increase the resilience of the transportation systems	Use infrastructure axes (motorways and primary roads) as ventilation corridors by planting trees in open spaces alongside roads. (Measure A1)

The large spatial scale of the adaptation measures proposed in this report shows that even more general policy recommendations, such as an increase in the number of trees in certain agricultural areas or unsealing, can result in a significant decrease in maximum temperatures and heat stress. This is particularly evident in urban areas and city centres.

Despite the correspondence in Table 1, care must be taken to verify that may affect the application of these recommendations at the AML and the local level. For example, although the increase in number of trees near infrastructure axes can increase the cooling system of these areas, there must be an evaluation of which areas can be more susceptible to forest fires in the future.

2.3.1. Spatial easements at the Lisbon Metropolitan Area resolution

Another point to consider is the legal framework for national and municipal programs of land use management and development (i.e. Public Law for Soil, Territorial Management and Urbanism, Law 31/2014³) that defines several easements that municipality must refer to, when planning territorial developments. The easements include sectorial plans for national security, environment, transportation, energy (among others) and special programs (Table 2).

² See catalogue of measures in Annex 1, page 72

³ The Public Law for Soil, Territorial Management and Urbanism dictates the basic principles for the sustainable development and national cohesion while safeguarding the economic, social, cultural and environmental functions of land uses. In addition, it intends to increase the territorial resilience to extreme climatic events and minimize de greenhouse gases emissions (Law 31/2014).

Table 2. Examples of easements and utility restrictions applicable to Lisbon Metropolitan Area municipalities.

National Network of Protected Areas – RNAP	
Areas with special relevance which require specific measures for conservation and management, i.e. through regulation of the artificial interventions that can degrade these areas. These areas are legally protected (Law n. ° 142/2008, de 24 de julho).	
Easements and utility restriction	Municipalities affected
Arrábida Natural Park	Sesimbra and Setúbal
Sintra-Cascais Natural Park	Sintra and Cascais
Tagus Estuary Natural Reserve	Vila Franca de Xira and Alcochete
Sado Estuary Natural Reserve	Setúbal and Palmela
Arriba Fóssil da Costa da Caparica Protected Landscape	Almada and Sesimbra
Lagosteiros Natural Monument	Sesimbra
Pedra da Mua Natural Monument	Sesimbra
Pedreira do Avelino Natural Monument	Sesimbra
Natura 2000 Network	
European ecological network composed of areas created under the Birds Directive (Special Protection Zones, Directive 79/409/EEC) and under the Habitat Directive (Special Conservation Zones, Council Directive 92/43/EEC). Human interventions in these areas should be compatible with the biodiversity and habitats preservation.	
Easements and type of utility restriction	Municipalities affected
Special Protection Zone (Birds Directive) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raso Cape • Espichel Cape and Lagoa Pequena • Tagus Estuary • Sado Estuary 	Mafra, Sintra and Cascais Sesimbra Vila Franca de Xira and Alcochete Setúbal and Palmela
Special Conservation Zone (Habitats Directive) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tagus Estuary • Sado Estuary • Lagoa de Albufeira 	Vila Franca de Xira and Alcochete Setúbal and Palmela Sesimbra
Coastline Program (POC)	
Program for the management and planning of the natural resources in the coastline.	
Easements and type of utility restriction	Municipalities affected
POC Cabo Espichel	Mafra, Sintra, Cascais, Almada and Sesimbra
POC Espichel-Odeceixe	Sesimbra and Setúbal

Special programs are particularly relevant for the work developed in the PROVIDE project because they are under specific regulatory jurisdiction (defined in the National Ecological Reserve), and consequently restrict the types of interventions or adaptation measures that can be done and in which area they can be applied (Figure 21, next page).

Figure 21. Four of the PROVIDE adaptation policy recommendations and corresponding spatial measures against heat stress overlaid with the easements and utility restrictions at the AML scale. Agroforestry systems (top left); Ecological systems (top right); Park systems (bottom left); Infrastructural verges (bottom right)

2.3.2. Challenges and opportunities at the municipal level

Public spaces in Lisbon Metropolitan Area represent a valuable opportunity to increase systemic resilience to climatic changes, through the creation of a network of green and blue infrastructures⁴. In fact, qualification projects in public spaces of Lisbon Metropolitan Area for the past 20 years have mostly focused on adaptation to high temperatures by creating green spaces with shaded areas and increasing urban agriculture presence (Santos, 2022).

Concern about the impact of heat stress on the population and territory of Almada and Lisbon has urged the study and implementation of adaptation measures at the local level. For example, the Lisboa Adaptation Hotspot is mainly composed of 'empty' urban spaces in a predominantly social housing area. It includes parts of an area that is currently the target of a major urban development plan, of public knowledge and widely promoted in

⁴ <https://metropublicnet.fa.ulisboa.pt/>

the media^{5,6,7,8,9,10}. The development intervention planned for the area, named “*Unidade de Execução de Marvila – Lisboa*” has just finished its Environmental Impact Assessment public consultation phase¹¹, having received 17 accepted contributions as of March 2024¹² (Figure 21).

Figure 22. Foreseen intervention area of the urban development plan of the “*Unidade de Execução de Marvila – Lisboa*” (in red). The project is expected to develop interventions (1) on public land use change, (2) on public and private buildings, and (3) on a major national railway system (dashed yellow line). Numbers in the legend (in Portuguese) read: Intervention area; Pavement surface area; Green spaces and equipment; Number of dwellings; Private parking; Public parking; Green Park area (Source: <https://lisboasecreta.co/nova-urbanizacao-em-marvila-e-beato/>)

In addition, the Lisbon Municipality is partner in the EU-LIFE LUNGS project¹³. The project intends to promote Lisbon’s resilience to the increase in temperatures and decrease in water availability. The EU-LIFE LUNGS is of relevance to PROVIDE, because it aims to increase shading areas and carbon sequestration through the plantation of trees and

⁵<https://www.publico.pt/2024/02/27/local/noticia/megaurbanizacao-marvila-enterrara-linha-norte-muda-zona-oriental-lisboa-2081750>

⁶<https://rr.sapo.pt/noticia/pais/2024/02/27/projeto-em-marvila-preve-eliminar-barreira-fisica-da-linha-ferroviaria/368582/>

⁷<https://www.timeout.pt/lisboa/pt/noticias/parque-verde-1500-casas-e-cobertura-da-linha-ferrea-vaio-transformar-zona-oriental-de-lisboa-022924>

⁸ <https://supercasa.pt/noticias/projeto-em-lisboa-quer-intervir-em-terrenos-vazios/n5316>

⁹<https://reportugal.vidaimobiliaria.com/atualidade/reabilitacao-urbana/lisboa-tem-10-projetos-estruturantes-curso-criar-mais-cidade/>

¹⁰ <https://lisboasecreta.co/nova-urbanizacao-em-marvila-e-beato/>

¹¹ <https://participa.pt/pt/consulta/unidade-de-execucao-ue-de-marvila>

¹² Not taken into full consideration in this document due to lack of analysis and discussion with the Lisbon Municipality. However, a preliminary quick scan reveals at least two contributions that mention “climate change”, “soil sealing”, “Urban Heat Island”, “green spaces” and other associated terms.

¹³ <https://life-lungs.lisboa.pt/>

bushes along infrastructural green areas (e.g., streets and green parks). The project has a stated preference for native vegetation when restoring urban green areas, through revegetating/planting trees or shrubs in urban and peri-urban areas. It considers the use of biodiverse evergreen pastures, possibly due to the natural adaptation strategies of these tree species to higher temperatures and lower water availabilities (David et al., 2007).

One of the key concerns of the PROVIDE team was to make best use of, and connect to, ongoing or foreseen climate action activities by its key stakeholders. The co-development process in PROVIDE helped to identify possible links to local adaptation efforts within Lisbon Metropolitan Area. As such, the EU-funded LIFE project COOLIFE ALMADA¹⁴ was signalled as of potential interest. This project aims to implement multifunctional solutions to help reduce temperatures in Almada urban areas as much as 3 °C, by creating an 'urban green corridor'.

COOLIFE ALMADA's area of proposed intervention is still under evaluation (as per the project's website). However, given the applied research nature of PROVIDE, the team decided to target the surrounding area as the Almada Adaptation Hotspot. This provided the opportunity to align the PROVIDE project's modelling activities at very high-resolution (1 m) with the adaptation knowledge needs of the Almada Municipality for that area. The novel concept of Adaptation Hotspots is an interesting approach to further develop, deploy and evaluate climate adaptation strategies at the Lisbon metropolitan and local scale.

Figure 23. Predicted area of intervention (in blue) of the COOLIFE ALMADA. The project is expected to support interventions (1) on public land use change (e.g., increasing vegetation density and unsealing), (2) on public and private buildings (e.g., application of green roofs and façades), (3) that reduce air temperature (e.g., increasing shaded areas where tree planting is not possible), and (4) that cool the population (e.g., heat refugia). Source: <https://www.cm-almada.pt/projeto-europeu-coolife-almada>

¹⁴ <https://www.cm-almada.pt/projeto-europeu-coolife-almada>

3. Adaptation scenario narratives for Islamabad¹⁵

Photo 5. A view of urban settings in the iconic city (IC3) of Islamabad, Pakistan. © Fahad Hanif

The capital city of Pakistan, Islamabad, is increasingly experiencing heat stress due to climate change, like many urban areas globally. In this Iconic region and city within the PROVIDE project, urban-modelling, local stakeholder engagement activities, surveys and semi-structured interviews in selected urban areas have highlighted the need for more knowledge and the insufficiency of robust data. Moreover, there is no available geospatial data at the city scale to conduct an urban-scale modelling which has limited the possibility to remodel the effects of the proposed adaptation measures to mitigate heat stress on the city scale. Therefore, the focus of our work has been to develop adaptation scenario narratives for one sector in Islamabad, sector E-11. This sector is a densely built area with a residential character, consisting primarily of single-family houses and a couple of newer developments with higher apartment buildings. Characteristic of the urban fabric is the presence of an older village (*Golra*) with more traditional morphology, which has been enveloped by the more recent expansion of Islamabad. In this process, also the natural landscape structure and water system have been impacted.

For this sector, more data has been available, based on the mapping of the regulation systems and the elaboration of the strategic spatial and adaptation profiles developed in the previous PROVIDE-reports D4.1 and D4.2. The results are evaluated in terms of their climate performance with the help of an iterative process. This implies the modelling and assessment of a first-draft adaptation scenario narrative, then an optimization and improvement of the adaptation measures and, finally, a second climate and impact modelling.

¹⁵ Main authors: Mariam Saleh Khan (WCS), Khadija Irfan (WCS), Raluca Davidel (BUUR PoS), and Niels Souverijns (VITO)

In what follows we describe the implementation of spatial measures and the resulted adaptation scenario narratives. Within the examined area of 2 by 2 km of sector E-11, four representative locations have been selected to explain in detail the implemented adaptation measures. The same locations are further highlighted in the presentation of the results of the climate impact modelling at meter-scale resolution. From this we have drawn general conclusions regarding future policy, planning and design guidelines. In the concluding discussion we explore the steps that could be taken to further disseminate this study and implement its results in the case of Islamabad.

Photo 6. The E-11 sector of Islamabad. © M.H. Toori

3.1. Adaptation narratives and design measures

While the focus in sector E-11 of Islamabad has been on adaptation measures related to heat stress, we also considered mitigation measures that would make the green-blue network more resilient to future flooding events. For this purpose, new infiltration zones were created, natural streams, which were diverted into narrow conduits, were reopened, and the demolition of properties that were encroaching in the drainage system has been proposed.

Figure 24 (next page) shows the adaptation scenario narrative high-resolution map that synthesises the existing and proposed spatial structures, while Figure 25 on page 40, focuses mainly on four applied measures:

- a. the development of green-blue corridors and green riparian zones
- b. the development of a system of urban forests and parks
- c. the establishment of green avenues and tree-lined streets
- d. proposals for climate resilient urban developments.

The first three measures contribute to lowering surface and air temperatures locally by providing shade and cooling through evapotranspiration. The fourth measure helps communities to protect themselves from heat stress through more adequate design of the built environment, while at the same time making sure that the natural environment is protected. This follows in line with a climate resilient development which seeks to optimize shade and ventilation on a structural level, while also integrate the existing

natural environment, e.g. water bodies, green corridors, etc. On an architectural level further design measures should also be considered, such as the use of reflective materials and proper insulation of buildings, natural cross ventilation, design of shadow facilities, green facades and roofs, etc.

Figure 24. High-resolution map overview of the general adaptation narrative for sector E-11 to better cope with higher temperatures, heat stress and associated extremes. Source: BUUR PoS, 2024

In the adaptation narrative for sector E-11, two green-blue corridors with additional green-riparian zones are proposed along the largest stream Jodh Kas and along a smaller 'nullah' in the south-eastern part of the sector. Besides providing urban cooling, these corridors offer people a place to relax, allow for the natural movement of wildlife, and include open space to absorb and filter rainwater. Additionally, to reduce flooding risks, the design includes flood plains in upstream areas and locations where flooding

was signaled by the hydrology study from 2022 (see PROVIDE-report D4.2, p. 67-68).

Several urban parks and forests were created in sector E-11 in such a way that all inhabitants can have access to a green space within a 5 minutes' walk from their homes (approximately 300 meters). In addition to their local climate effects, these areas provide shelter to wildlife and recreational areas for city dwellers, including added health benefits. Many of the streets in sector E-11 already have linear green structures which form natural canopies and protect pedestrians from sun. When aligned with the direction of prevailing winds, they can also facilitate the flow of cool air into the city. Therefore, the adaptation scenario narrative map below highlights only the areas where this strategy can be reinforced with, for example, the building of green avenues that help to connect green spaces within the urban fabric.

Figure 25. Spatial strategies and measures composing the adaptation scenario narrative for sector E-11, Islamabad: a) green blue corridors and green riparian zones, b) urban forests and parks, c) green avenues and tree-lined streets, and d) climate resilient urban developments. Source: BUUR PoS, 2024

Since the heat stress model is focusing mainly on the outdoor spaces, the proposed adaptation narrative is primarily integrating quantifiable measures that are structural for the outdoor spaces. However, for an optimum result, also other nature-based measures on building level or in the design of public space, should be considered when implementing new planning regulations. Overall, the proposed adaptation narratives and designs are meant to be suggestions that illustrate the potential for different adaptation measures of sector E-11. For example, Figure 26 below explains how different heat regulation measures, e.g. planting of trees and opening up of previously closed-off streams, can be embedded in the urban fabric. Such an intervention would provide shade and cooling during high temperatures and reduce heat stress and associated extremes. At the same time, the proposal creates space for new mixed developments, offering a green, qualitative and climate-proof living environment for the inhabitants of the growing city of Islamabad.

Figure 26. Left: Aerial view of the current situation in a selected part of sector E-11. Right: Illustration of proposed adaptation plan against higher temperatures. Source: BUUR PoS, 2024

In Figure 27 (next page) is a horizontal cross-cut of the same selected spot in E-11 which shows the relationship between different heat regulation measures and their embeddedness within the urban fabric. The adaptation measures offer a solution for certain climate risks, but also bring many co-benefits. The presence of water and greenage lowers the heat stress and creates room for biodiversity and recreation and improves air quality. In the new housing development maximum attention needs to be given to sustainable wastewater treatment, reducing the present pollution of the streams. By de-sealing surfaces and creating natural water retention and infiltration zones, the flood risk is reduced, but also the groundwater level can be restored, the soil stabilized, and drought

problems diminished. The result is a safe and pleasant living environment, that also has true ecological value.

Figure 27. Illustrative section of the selected spot in sector E-11 showing the relations between different heat regulation measures. Source: BUUR PoS, 2024

3.1.1. Four strategic adaptation hotspot locations in sector E-11

In the case of sector E-11 we have selected four strategic locations (see Figure 28, next page) for an in-depth analysis due to their previous identification as hotspots for high heat stress (see the heat stress modelling in PROVIDE-report D4.2). This involves both nature-based solutions to avoid high temperatures as well as design measures on how to build a more heat-resistant urban area:

Location 1 depicts a mixed-use development, situated along the main boulevard crossing sector E-11 from east to west. Firstly, we focus on strengthening the green blue corridor along the ‘nullah’ – the main boulevard - and, secondly, on the design of four urban blocks with an open structure and shadow-rich semi-public and public spaces. This composition allows for more natural light and ventilation to the buildings, while also respecting the autonomy of different types of buildings.

Location 2 shows a new residential area that is a reinterpretation of the existing urban fabric with two- to three-story houses densely built next to each other. According to the results from the previous heat modelling, this is a very efficient strategy to provide shaded space without the need for vegetation. This type of design is combined with a generous urban park in walking distance from the neighbourhood and connected to it through tree-lined streets. In the direct vicinity of the park, larger building structures (for e.g. schools, mosques, commercial facilities, etc.) could be placed, so that they can take advantage of the shade and cooling provided by the high vegetation. Moreover, the semi-private spaces of the internal courtyards also have a green character and can provide extra cooling through the design of water retention areas.

Location 3 shows the structural role of green blue corridors and green riparian zones. It is situated along the natural stream Nala 03, where a bend of the stream was covered to reclaim land for property development, and then the straightened drainage path was converted into a concrete conduit of an insufficient cross section. Due to the high risk of flooding and the high heat stress produced by the high percentage of sealed surfaces, the design shows a solution where the conduit is removed and the riverbed re-naturalized. Furthermore, green riparian zones were added along the corridor to increase biodiversity in the area and create extra buffer space for water infiltration.

Location 4 shows the possibility to gradually transform the service area with large buildings built on the south-east edge of sector E-11 into a better structured area. This would mean to create more unsealed surfaces and high vegetation, as well as cool spots which are reachable within walking distance.

Below is a figure showing what the adaptation narratives may look like in sector E-11.

Figure 28. Illustration of possible adaptation measures to be implemented in Location 1-4. Source: BUUR PoS, 2024

3.2. Evaluation of the adaptation measures

3.2.1. Modelling of adaptation options

An important part of the work on adaptation scenario narratives is that we have taken the nature-based solutions and new building setups designed above and modelled them to examine their actual effects on heat stress reduction. For this, we selected a hot day during present day summer period (2020-07-10) to calculate heat stress at a meter-scale level. We have used the Wet Bulb Globe Temperature to indicate heat stress levels (considering temperatures, humidity and radiation) and categorize the heat stress into different categories, depending on the severity of heat stress that is experienced based on ISO norms (ISO:7243).

The current land use in sector E-11 of Islamabad exhibits large areas of very high and extreme heat stress (see the left-most panel in Figure 29). Although there are some areas with vegetation they are limited in size and abundance, and the number of trees is limited. This is essential since trees are the most effective measures that reduce heat stress. Moreover, the centrality of trees is reflected in the adaptation scenario narratives, where the areas with tree-planting have a better heat index. The new heat index in areas with trees is only reaching ‘strong’ heat stress levels instead of ‘very strong’ or ‘extreme’, reducing WBGT by 3°C or 2 heat stress categories (Figure 29, the panel in the middle). Apart from trees, also buildings help shade lowers heat stress by one category. A combination of both trees and high, shading buildings provides the optimal setup for reducing heat stress in sector E-11.

Figure 29. Daytime heat stress at 16h local time in the E-11 sector during a hot day in summer (2020-07-10). (left) current land use (middle) proposed adaptation strategy based on section 3.2.1. (right) difference in Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT) between both. Source: VITO

The importance of both trees and high buildings becomes even more clear when zooming in on the four selected strategic locations mentioned above (see Figure 30, next page). Location 1 showcases the benefits of the large tree planting near the area of the nullah (the boulevard), creating a cool oasis transversing the city. The new building setup with large open spaces with trees offers both a pleasant environment and cool areas, as well as lowers energy costs for cooling of the buildings surrounding the open spaces by providing shade to direct sunlight. In Location 2, the adaptation measures proposed provide more densely built structures with trees in the narrow streets, offering a more traditional setup. Despite the higher concentration of buildings, often their shade lowers heat stress levels from extreme to very high numbers. The streets are characterized by trees and the large green infrastructure nearby offer spots that are cooler. Moreover, the cooling effect of trees is also visible in Location 3 and 4.

Figure 30. Daytime heat stress at 16h local time in the E-11 sector during a hot day in summer (2020-07-10). Zoomed in areas highlight the effect of adaptation measures that were defined in Figure 28 (page 43) on heat stress alleviation. Source: VITO

3.2.2. Impact of adaptation options

Based on the previous analysis, we see that trees offer effective ways of providing relief of heat stress in the city. Generally, one can lower two levels of heat stress in the E-11 sector in a neighbourhood of trees, in this case, from extreme to high levels. This is also reflected when averaging heat stress over the full E-11 sector. With climate change, heat stress will rise towards the future in Islamabad. In a *Current Policies* scenario, we notice that heat-stress levels can rise, regardless of planting trees in specific areas. By the end of the century this can lead to very high heat stress levels, also in the areas that are considered zones to offer cooling, which can lead to problematic situations. Such levels not only provide health risks, but trees are often the only natural cooling spots for citizens that cannot afford air-conditioning. An important note is to be made regarding the spatial extent of the cooling that trees provide. The highest heat stress reductions are achieved in the direct neighbourhood of trees, and their cooling effect dissipates quickly when further away from the tree crowns.

Figure 31. a) Average heat stress over different land cover types in the E-11 sector and their evolution towards the end of the century under a Current Policies scenario. b) The spatial evolution of the cooling effect of trees within the E-11 sector.

3.3. Implementation strategies and next steps

The adaptation interventions proposed above focus on mitigating heat stress and urban flooding, two of the most prominent climatic threats faced by the city of Islamabad. In doing so, these measures also consider the increasing need of housing driven by the capital's rapid population growth. These interventions, mainly categorizable under infrastructure improvements, expansion of urban green spaces/afforestation and water management sectors, align very closely with the overarching vision of adaptation component in the existing national level policies, plans, and projects.

In Pakistan, preservation of ecological assets has consistently been a core focus of environmental and developmental policies, albeit with limited implementation. Hence, it is important to note that the reimagined spatial structures explored in this project, and the reinforced blue-green corridors, offer adaptation options that are both implementable and cost-effective. Additionally, they are sustainable nature-based solutions which adhere to the strategies envisioned in several key policies such as National Climate Change Policy and National Water Policy. Moreover, they comply with enforceable plans including the Green Building Code, National Adaptation Plan, and fit well under large-scale projects of Green Pakistan Program, such as Ten Billion Tree Tsunami, The Living Indus Projects, Protected Areas Initiative, and Miyawaki Urban Forests initiative. Table 3 on the next page highlights the synergies between the proposed adaptation scenario narrative measures and the national developmental roadmap accentuated in prominent policies and projects.

Table 3. Provisions and measures highlighted in Pakistan's national policies and mega projects that align with proposed implementation options

Policy/Plan /Project	Envisioned Interventions	Postulates from Adaptation Narrative
National Adaptation Plan	Mainstream land and water management through forest planting, land reclamation structures, and restoring degraded ecosystems.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop green-blue corridors and green riparian zones. • Grow an interconnected system of urban forests and parks.
	Introduce better land use planning and control measures to ensure that settlements do not occur in flood prone areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reopen natural streams which are diverted into narrow conduits and demolish the properties that are encroaching in the drainage system.
	<p>Identify and introduce NBS initiatives to enable adaptation and to tackle urban heat, urban water scarcity, and flood risks</p> <p>Identify opportunities to scale up urban forest projects</p> <p>Construct open to help control storm water by capturing runoff</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop green-blue corridors and green riparian zones • Establish green avenues and tree-lined streets. • Develop a system of urban forests and parks. • Create new infiltration zones.
National Climate Change Policy	<p>To promote tree plantation, conservation of natural resources, nature-based solutions and long-term sustainability.</p> <p>Signify the importance of forests to mitigate extreme weather events including heat waves, floods.</p> <p>Aggressively pursue afforestation and reforestation programs with plantation suited to the effects of climate change</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a system of urban forests and parks. • Develop green-blue corridors and green riparian zones. • Establish green avenues and tree-lined streets.
National Water Policy	Several measures proposed for watershed management and conservation, prevention of encroachment on natural streams, and restricting development in flood prone areas.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop green-blue corridors and green riparian zones. • Reopen natural streams which are diverted into narrow conduits and demolish the properties that are encroaching in the drainage system.
Green Building Code	Provisions stress on; a) maintenance of trees and vegetation at urban development sites to mitigate heat stress, b) development must not cause ecological impairment especially with respect to passage of storm water, c) Enhancement of (non-polluted) water infiltration d) prohibition of development in flood prone areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish green avenues and tree-lined streets. • Develop green-blue corridors and green riparian zones. • Creation of new infiltration zones.
Billion Tree Tsunami and Miyawaki Urban Forests Initiative	Enhancement of forest cover through; road and canal side plantation, and enhancing urban tree cover	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a system of urban forests and parks. • Establish green avenues and tree-lined streets.
Living Indus	Envisions an ambitious urban forestation along water channels, green infrastructure for flood control and watershed management.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop green-blue corridors and green riparian zones. • Develop a system of urban forests and parks.

3.3.1. Proposed adaptation strategies for sector E-11

The proposed adaptation scenario narratives for sector E-11 are mainly incorporating nature-based solutions consistent with core focus of the current climate change and developmental policies as well as ongoing projects. For example, the afforestation could be enhanced in collaboration with existing forestation projects as mentioned in the table above. Furthermore, in public parks and other urban green belts, the use of native tree species that are heat resilient, need less water, and provide more shade, would be the most effective in reducing the negative impacts of urban heat. These native species of trees or shrubs in general urban or peri-urban space can also favour local ecosystem and increase its overall climate resilience. With this, development of green-blue corridors plus restructuring to remove residential and commercial settlement from some urban areas prone to monsoon floods may become crucial to prevent persistent damages.

Moreover, the broadening and opening-up of water channels and greening of blue corridors would help accommodate floodwater and provide protection to surrounding communities. The green building code enlists requirements that must be fulfilled at every developmental site. Tree plantation and maintenance of vegetation fall among these coded provisions and could mainstream proposed patterns of urban afforestation and maintenance of green belts within the city centres to curb heat stress. Thus, implementation of all these adaptation interventions should emphasize climate-smart urban planning, ensuring infrastructure resilience, sustainable water use, and careful consideration of policy guidelines or restrictions.

In addition to existing strategy documents, there is a pressing need to develop context-specific, climate-smart urban plans in more sectors of Islamabad. These plans should be tailored to the local needs of individual communities through detailed interventions, moving beyond general preventive guidelines. They must proactively address climatic threats, such as heat stress, by integrating them into development planning rather than treating them as passing seasonal challenges. Furthermore, these plans should be inclusive, addressing the needs of marginalized communities and gender considerations. Adopting a bottom-up approach, local-level plans should then converge to inform provincial policies, which in turn should provide clear guidelines for integration into the national framework and shape priority actions that ensure alignment with international commitments.

However, the development of context-responsive plans and effective policies hinges on the availability of comprehensive data, both quantitative and qualitative, a lack which was identified as the most significant challenge during our project work. In addition, there is a noticeable gap in research exploring the local impacts of climatic extremes. Our surveys and interviews conducted with local stakeholders and inhabitants in Islamabad (for indoor and outdoor settings) have revealed that middle and lower-income segments, which constitute a significant portion of the city's population, lack the capacity to adapt to heat stress. Challenges range from the unaffordability of cooling mechanisms to the nature of outdoor work that exposes individuals to extreme heat for extended periods of time. Such limitations are often overlooked in policy documents and city planning.

Thus, for more informed decision making it is crucial to improve data collection methods that actively track the negative impacts of climate change on various aspects of social wellbeing, including spatial development, health, labour productivity, agriculture, and energy demand etc. Moreover, the use of technology, such as IoT sensors for real time data collection of temperature, humidity and urban heat islands, can facilitate the process and provide more accurate data for further local impact analyses. Ideally, such a system should also consider inputs from local communities, authorities, and researchers. When

a robust databank is established, it should be publicly accessible to further enhance research efforts and enable data-driven adaptation strategies.

Importantly, public awareness and local community initiatives are essential when formulating an efficient adaptation strategy. It is central to inform, educate, and engage both local policy makers and inhabitants about climate change impacts and effective adaptation measures. This can be done through multimedia campaigns, workshops, community meetings, and other collaborative efforts between media, educational institutions and civil society organizations. Furthermore, it is essential to ensure that the adaptation measures are inclusive of all and particularly benefit the vulnerable or marginalized segments of the community. Women groups, children and people with special needs can also become more included in active processes of planning and decision-making, via, for example, community-driven initiatives of afforestation, local water management and gender-specific health interventions.

Moreover, there are major barriers in implementation of these adaptation strategies due to economic constraints and lack of capacity, both in the context of expertise and knowledge. Appropriate knowledge or expertise for making use of available international climate finance through Green Climate Fund (GCF) or Global Environment Facility (GEF) are also very limited. Furthermore, additional finance mobilization through public-private partnership is confined due to lack of trust on the governance system and non-provision of incentives which lays a huge responsibility on the bureaucratic system to make reforms. Institutional capacity needs to be built through targeted programs and training workshops focused on technical skills, project management capabilities, and a better understanding of climate risks and adaptation solutions. Additionally, fostering a collaborative environment both at horizontal and vertical levels within government agencies and with local authorities, NGOs, and international partners is essential to ensure efficient utilization of the available resources.

In summary, addressing climate change impacts in Islamabad requires an integrated approach that involves transformation and building of new infrastructure, policy cohesion, efficient data collection, both quantitative and qualitative, and incentivizing public involvement. By prioritizing data-driven strategies, context-specific planning and ensuring that local insights inform provincial and national policies, a resilient and adaptive framework could be developed that addresses the challenges posed by climate change. This comprehensive approach not only enhances local capacity to cope with climatic threats but also aligns with broader provincial, national, and international objectives, fostering sustainable development and equitable resilience with improved well-being and quality of life for all the residents of urban areas.

4. Adaptation scenario narratives for Bodø¹⁶

Photo 7. The city of Bodø on the peninsula © H. G. Lindberg

Bodø is one of the most important cities in northern Norway, and part of the iconic region Arctic Fennoscandia. We refer to the two previous PROVIDE-reports (D4.1 and D4.2) on more details and description of this region and Bodø Municipality. The previous investigation of the spatial structure of the city pointed out which spatial systems are in place to act as regulators against heat, drought or flooding, among other things, in the event of extreme climate change. Moreover, the modelling using the Flood4Cast-model in the previous report highlighted pluvial and fluvial flooding as the central climate risks in Bodø. While the flood risk has been identified to not be extremely high but can locally cause temporary inconveniences. Thus, we look at floods as well as heat impacts in the following adaptation scenario narrative. In addition, together with local stakeholders, we have co-developed a broader vision of sustainable and resilient development for the urban areas in Bodø.

From the UrbClim-model analysis we know that the perceived temperature level will rise in Bodø. In addition, both the mean daily minimum temperature and the mean daily maximum temperature will increase by about 2 to 3 °C by 2100. The annual number of heatwave days will double in urban areas, from 20 to 25 today to 50 to 60 in 2100. The urban heat island effect plays a very strong role in this, with temperature differences between the city centre and the hills around the city of 1.25° during the day, but almost 2.5° at night.

Although the effective values of the perceived temperature in Bodø in 2100 will remain much lower than in cities in more Southern countries, there is a noticeable warming that can have an impact on inhabitants and ecosystems in Bodø. In addition, buildings in Bodø are much less prepared for heat days.

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Figure 32. UrbClim modelling of mean daily minimum temperature today and in 2100 (top left), mean daily maximum temperature today and in 2100 (top right), yearly heatwave days today and in 2100 (bottom left) and heat island effect day and night in 2100 (bottom right). Source: VITO

The Flood4Cast modelling shows several zones in Bodø that are more prone to flooding. That is in the first place the open space area around the Bodøelva river. The stream does not have sufficient capacity to drain all the water immediately during heavy rainfall, so that local flooding occurs on the banks, especially at the junctions with the larger road infrastructure, with a flood depth of ca. 0,5 – 1 meter. In addition, there is a risk of flooding in a number of residential areas outside the city centre, where the capacity of the sewerage system is insufficient to swallow large amounts of rainwater, but here the water depth is never more than 20-30 cm.

Figure 33. Flood4Cast modelling results showing the potential flood water depth during a 100-years-flood for 2100. Source: VITO

Figure 34. Zoom of Flood4cast results and aerial photo (modified from Google Earth) of the mostly affected area along the Bodøelva river. Source: VITO

In the adaptation scenario narrative below, we look at the green-blue infrastructure in Bodø, which has a role to play in buffering rainwater locally and at the same time providing cooling during hot days. In doing so, we focus on the existing open spaces around the stream but also at the urban fabric within the city itself.

Since there were no major climate risks resulting from the Flood4Cast modelling, we decided not to carry out a second modelling for Bodø to evaluate the adaptation options. Instead, an alternative route was devised in which the evaluation of the adaptation measures was done through a combination of site visits and a creative workshop carried out by an urban planner and local researchers within the PROVIDE-team in Bodø with invited local stakeholders. During the workshop, the theme of the adaptation scenario narrative was broadened up to include a more proactive view on sustainable, resilient spatial developments for Bodø.

4.1. Adaptation narratives and design measures

To reduce the impact of heat stress, there are numerous measures that can be taken. These have already been discussed in detail in the Lisbon and Islamabad cases and a long list of possible measures can be consulted in Annex 1 (see page 72). In Bodø, we chose to focus on nature-based solutions that both reduce the risk of heat stress and help to provide infiltration and drainage for pluvial flooding and potential droughts. This mainly involves softening the soil and creating green corridors with sufficient tree shade.

Bodø has a lot of paved surfaces, especially in the areas with industry and large retail outlets, and there is not much vegetation in the city centre. That is why we propose to work on both the de-sealing and greening of the industrial zones and the parking lots there, as well as the potential to green important streets and boulevards with more trees and create green zones where there is also room for rainwater infiltration. Moreover, these green axes can act as connections between the parks and other green public places that already exist in Bodø to form a coherent green network. Extremely paved areas, such as the entire area around the City Nord shopping centre and the harbour district north of the city's train station, can be transformed into green areas within this network. It is precisely

here that there is a lot of open space, often underutilized, where greening can really have positive effects on both climate and the environment.

Photo 8. Examples of areas in Bodø with a lot of sealed surfaces and a clear lack of green space or elements
© M. De Paep

The open space area along the Bodøelva stream is a strategic green lung that extends to the urban fabric. It already plays an important role today as a recreational zone, but also as a place for food production, both professionally and through urban farming initiatives. To reduce the risk of flooding along the stream, we propose to set up zones for water buffering with weirs and infiltration pools, so that in the event of flooding, drainage does not have to be resorted to immediately. This increases the capacity of the stream as well as creates more room for natural water infiltration, which prevents drought in this important green zone. Special attention should be paid to the bottleneck that is now created at the intersection of the road infrastructure, additional water buffering is best created here or directly upstream.

Figure 35. Strategic vision for the city center of Bodø with green parks connected through green corridors along main routes and streets. Source: BUUR PoS, 2024

Figure 36. Zoom of the general strategic vision with a design proposal for the greening of the area of the City Nord Shopping Mall and measures for water retention along the Bodøelva river. Source: BUUR PoS, 2024

4.2. Evaluation of the adaptation options

In June 2024, several site visits were conducted to the locations mentioned in this adaptation strategy. While our examinations had been from afar and via existing modelling data, we learned that many of the proposed measures had already been implemented in the recent past. For example, a buffer zone had been created along the Bodøelva stream, at the location of the junction with the road infrastructure, to increase capacity. This buffer zone also serves as a place for recreation and is spatially integrated very nicely into the natural environment. Upstream, the natural meandering of the stream has been preserved so that the capacity also increases here, the flow is inhibited in a natural way and more opportunities for natural infiltration are created.

Photo 9. Recently realized water retention and buffer zone along the Bodøelva river in Bodø, that also serves as a recreation area © M. De Paep

Within the city centre, many streets designated as green corridors appear to have already been laid out in this way in practice, with trees providing shade. However, there are still areas for improvement: In the more recently redesigned streets, the trees often have too little space to really grow into large specimens with a sufficiently shading tree crown. There has been very little attention given to soften and green the space under the trees, and hardly anywhere has there been thought of wadis that can serve as natural infiltration zones within the urban fabric.

Photo 10. Good examples of green zones with space for rainwater infiltration and shadow from trees in the urban area of Bodø © M. De Paep

Moreover, the harbour district and the area around the shopping district City Nord still have an enormous degree of asphalt paving, while there is plenty of space for greenery, trees and semi-paving. Furthermore, the parks marked on the map (see Figure 35, page 53), in particular the cemetery in the south of the city by the airport, the Rensås Park in the northeast, and Pelle Molins park at the coast in the west, are real green oases that offer cooling and relaxation to the inhabitants. In the city centre itself, however, much of the recently redesigned public space (some of which is still under construction) is of high quality in terms of materials and architecture, but the proportion of greenery remains very limited.

During the workshop with local experts, these general insights were further confirmed. To further open up the discussion and narrative, we had a conversation during the workshop about how Bodø should evolve further in the next 25 years to be truly sustainable and resilient, and a good place to live also in the future. The participants were asked to discuss and draw on maps showing the city of Bodø as well as the whole municipality (including non-urban spaces). In doing so, we shifted the focus from the risks and looked at the important systems that are present in a city: economic activities, food production and distribution, housing and quality of life, and nature and ecology. For each theme, we asked the attendees what qualities there are to protect in Bodø, what things can be improved, what major threats they see and what the overarching ambition should be for urban development. Of course, climate change always plays a role in this, but other, more socially oriented evolutions also have a major impact on these themes.

Thus, the final adaptation scenario narratives for Bodø consists of broad sustainability ambitions in four themes: Ecology, Economy and transport, Food, and Quality of life. Below follows descriptions and summaries from the discussions with the local stakeholders during the workshop, together with a summarised illustration of the maps the participants drew on during the workshop:

4.2.1. Ecology

- To make room for resilient and climate-resistant nature in urban spaces we can protect ecosystems as well as contribute to climate adaptation against heat, drought, and flooding.
- There are several large development projects in the pipeline in Bodø, first and foremost on the site of the current airport which will be moved to make space for a whole new part of the city. It will be important in such development projects that open spaces are preserved as much as possible and that no ecosystem values are lost. At the same time, new projects must also provide new, high-quality green and blue spaces.
- In addition, work must be done step by step to develop a strong green-blue network throughout the urban fabric in Bodø. The existing parks, green spaces and avenues form the backbone of this must be strengthened and expanded, and more squares and paved areas need to be de-paved and greened. Natural streams that have been diverted underground should be re-opened and re-naturalized where possible.
- In Bodø, private gardens play a crucial role since they take up a lot of space. Private owners must be encouraged to make their gardens more biodiverse and to pay more attention to an ecologic management, in terms of mowing and species selection. This also means to increase awareness about how a seemingly wild, more free-growing garden is a more ecologically valuable garden. This includes attention to native species and less invasive and/or exotic plants. By extension, this also applies to agricultural and forestry areas where more attention should be placed on increasing biodiversity and decreasing monoculture.

Figure 37. Notes on map of Bodø under the theme Ecology.

Details:

1 = Areas with development pressure (e.g. „downbuilding“ of natural spaces and arable land)

2 = Valuable ecological areas where the old military airbase is located and where the new airport is being planned.

3 = Biologically diverse areas along the coast, chalk-rich.

4.2.2. Economy and transport

- As a relatively remote city, protecting the accessibility of Bodø is crucial for its prosperity. Moreover, in extreme (climate) conditions, Bodø remains highly dependent on its relationship with other cities and the national infrastructures. Thus, the accessibility via air, boat, road and rail are crucial, and while infrastructure is in place it could be improved to handle unexpected events. Special attention should be paid to issues such as avalanche security of the (road and rail) infrastructure.

- There is a need for a clear modal shift towards more sustainable mobility, especially for internal travels within Bodø itself. This means additional investments in cycling infrastructure, expansion of the public bus services and local ferry connections, and more attention to the role of alternative mobility modes, such as (electric) scooters, car-sharing or community carpooling. In the relatively short term, there is also a need for electrification, not only of passenger cars, but also of logistics, trains, boats and perhaps even air traffic.
- Local trade and industry must be protected as much as possible, and their resilience increased – against climate change, but also against the impacts of globalization (i.e. internet shopping and imports). A compact city like Bodø has all the assets to focus on a small-scale economy and trade, well integrated into the urban fabric with proximity as a major asset, both in terms of society and mobility.
- A specific proposal is to integrate Nord University, currently located in the suburbs, more strongly into the city and perhaps even move to the city centre in the long term. This would ensure proximity and shorter travel distances for employees and students but also have a positive impact on the liveliness of the city centre and potentially the income of local businesses.

Figure 38. Notes on map of Bodø under the theme Economy and transport.

Details:
1 = Railway station. Important to improve conditions (maintenance) and increase capacity.

2 = Airport. Domestic flights are important transportations for inhabitants.

4.2.3. Food

- Norway does not have enough domestic food production to be self-sufficient but relies on imports to feed its inhabitants (as well as livestock). This is a vulnerability that could cause major problems in the event of a climate crisis and cascading effects of impacts elsewhere in the world.
- Thus, in Bodø it is central to have a maximum protection of existing agricultural land and a focus on broad integration of (although small-scale) farming initiatives. This concerns, for example, ongoing community agriculture and urban farming but also the promotion of vegetable gardens on one's own plot or planting fruit trees in public spaces. Protecting water quality for fishing is also an important task.
- In addition, there must also be a better market for local products. In-house production or community-based agriculture are then supplemented by a local farmers' and fish market, where local products from the immediate but also wider surroundings of Bodø are offered.

Figure 39. Notes on map of Bodø under the theme Food.

Details:
Shaded, green areas show potential land for local food production that could be further utilized to increase the degree of food security.

4.2.4. Quality of life

- Bodø is a city where people like to live, and that quality must continue to be assured in the future. A huge asset is the direct contact between the urban city and the surrounding wilderness, mountains and sea. Thus, open and nature spaces must be protected as much as possible, and a further growth of the city must mainly take place internally, through densification of the already built areas.
- The city must remain inclusive and pay greater attention to a wide range of services and infrastructures for all inhabitants, especially children and the elderly. Thus, the design of public spaces must pay extra attention to these groups, but also to the range and variety of sports and recreational activities, mobility (public transport), (public) services and (affordable) housing.
- All participants, including the representatives from Bodø Municipality, emphasized the importance of a strong and decisive city government, with a clear vision and the will and resources to realize it. This means, among other things, that they focus on local inhabitants' quality of life and do not get pre-occupied with the promises of large private developments, mega projects, or disruptive tourism. In addition, there must be better quality control of ambitious projects so that the high ambitions are maintained until the final implementation.

Figure 40. Notes on map of Bodø under the theme Quality of life. Shows the perceived threats as well as opportunities within the existing urban fabric and reuse of, for example, the current and future airports.

4.3. Implementation strategies and next steps

From the initial engagement with local stakeholders within the PROVIDE project we have been aware of the high level of adaptive capacity that exists within Bodø Municipality, although the climate impacts foreseen in the modelled adaptation narrative scenarios do not present such extreme events and dangers to human lives as in the other three iconic regions and cities. There is, however, uncertainty about future climate impacts and the need to plan and invest accordingly. For example, the preservation of existing agricultural and arable land depends on the position of the prevailing local political regime.

The proposed adaptation measures in this report, e.g. to green the city centre, undoing the pavements of the industrial and shopping area, and making streams naturally open and increase natural runoff, all require committed investments and political will to implement and finalise. Hence, in the finalisation of PROVIDE, the local researchers will emphasise communication efforts with targeted audiences, such as local planning officers, urban planners, architects, decision-makers and politicians, as well as schools and non-governmental organisations to enhance the local knowledge and awareness of current and future climate change impacts, emphasising urban challenges and nature-based solutions, and how urban design can both increase resilience and adaptation capacity as well as the overall quality of life in Bodø.

5. Adaptation scenario narratives for Nassau¹⁷

Photo 11. Islands of The Bahamas © The Bahamas Ministry of Tourism & Aviation

On the island of New Providence on the northeastern edge of the West Indies in the Atlantic Ocean, lies the capital city of Bahamas, Nassau, in the Caribbean islands. Two climate hazards were identified in the previous co-development process within the PROVIDE project by national stakeholders as hazards of existing and emerging concerns: tropical cyclones and heat. The Bahamas generally shows a strong trend of increasing storm surge risk from tropical cyclones due to sea level rise, by up to 1500% by 2100. Tropical cyclone frequency and intensity will increase by less than 5% under SSP1-1.9 and SSP534 overshoot scenarios by 2100; tropical cyclones frequency and intensity will increase up to 20% with large uncertainties, under an SSP585 scenario. As such, sea-level rise emerged as the main driver of concern for tropical cyclone impacts. Heatwaves will strongly increase in Nassau and New Providence Island, with heatwave impacts increasing up to 800% by 2100 compared to present-day conditions. Whereas storm surge impacts will not peak and decline under an overshoot scenario, heat impacts are likely to peak and decline under overshoot.

Via co-development processes with local stakeholders and climate and impacts modelling conducted in our previous work, we here present adaptation scenario narratives for Nassau and New Providence Island. Presented first are the results from the climate and impact modelling of the adaptation narratives and the spatial conclusions that can be drawn to further guide policy, planning and design. Secondly, we discuss the contextual specificity of Nassau and the Bahamas and the particularities it entails for the implementation of the study and its results.

5.1. Adaptation narratives and design measures

In our previous work, the PROVIDE team has mapped the spatial structures of the island of New Providence that are critical for its adaptation to higher temperatures and the

¹⁷ Main authors: Rosanne Martyr-Koller (CA), Severine Hermand and Mario Doneddu (BUUR PoS), and Chahan Kropf (ETH).

mitigation of the effects of tropical cyclones. For more details about the Bahamas and Nassau we refer to the work in PROVIDE reports D4.1 and D4.2. The overall approach used in this work is illustrated in Figure 41.

Figure 41. Research, planning and design methodology developed for the elaboration of adaptation narratives of the island of New Providence to higher temperatures, heat stress and associated extremes from tropical cyclones. Source: BUUR PoS, 2024

The premise is that to address the above risks, space must be organized in such a way so as to provide heat, wind and coastal flooding regulation services. For space to provide such services it has to be organized in such a way so as shading, evapotranspiration, heat reflection/emission functions are manifested, together with protection from extreme winds and waves. The manifestation of the aforementioned spatial functions is furthered by a series of corresponding policy-level recommendations for the implementation of a set of specific spatial measures.

In their abstract form, policy recommendations take the form of generalized strategic guidelines to promote soil unsealing (and, thus, reduce heat absorption by hard surfaces and the experience of heat stress around them), increase ecological density and surface water (and, thus, increase cooling through evapotranspiration), promote the ventilation of air currents throughout the urbanized landscape (and, thus, decrease the UHI effect), provide coastal protection (and, thus, accommodate excess water), and, finally, strategically and tactically structurally enhance and dry-/wet-proof buildings.

The application of the above policy recommendations is done by concrete measures that are implemented in space:

1. green avenues and tree-lined streets, resulting in more greenery in the streetscape, along with the enhancement of private

- gardens, industrial areas, and parking lots, transforming traditionally paved surfaces into vegetation,
2. urban, peri-urban and regional parks and forests, expanding the presence of tall vegetation across the entire landscape, specifically nearby areas impacted by elevated temperatures and heat extremes,
3. green ventilation corridors, creating a rise in green linear features crossing the urban spaces, linking them to surrounding countryside and facilitating air circulation.,
4. dikes, sea walls and water retention areas, that is, the accommodation of excess water, and
5. strengthening of foundations and dry-/wet-proofing of buildings, that is, the provision of comfortable indoor conditions.

Figure 42. Measure card from the catalogue (see Annex 1, page 72) showing the evaluation and co-benefits of green ventilation corridors. Source: BUUR PoS, 2024

5.1.1. Tropical cyclones adaptation

Figure 43 shows a high-resolution map with the overall adaptation narrative for the island of New Providence to tropical cyclones. This is done through three sets of spatial measures: First, a **coastal protection strategy** that focuses on raising land or constructing soft or hard barriers against tidal waves – for example, using dune zones, mangrove forests or seaweed plantations, and/or levees, depending on the geomorphology of the surface. Such barriers can assist in the protection of the urbanized edges of the New Providence Island. The parts of the island that are prone to coastal flooding necessitate further **flood protection** – for example, using dikes and water retention areas, and the structural adaptation of buildings (e.g. building on piles or dry-/wet-proofing basements, ground floors etc.). Finally, due to the prevalence of winds – primarily with an eastern direction but also along the north-south axis – the **structural adaptation** of buildings foundations, frames and materials is considered necessary.

Figure 43. Cumulative adaptation scenario narrative of the island of New Providence against tropical cyclones extremes. Source: BUUR PoS, 2024

5.1.2. Heat adaptation

Figure 44 below shows the overall adaptation scenario narrative for the island of New Providence to heat stress. This is done through three spatial measures. Firstly, an increase in high vegetation both in terms of spaces within the urban fabric as well as an expansion of current areas of ecological value, is envisioned to provide a higher amount of cooling surfaces that reduces heat. Secondly, the urban fabric is suggested to undergo a generalized soil unsealing strategy, replacing hard surfaces with more permeable surfaces with low vegetation. And finally, tree-lined mobility axes that traverse the urban fabric and connect the core of the island with its edges are designed to promote the ventilation of air currents.

Figure 44. Cummulative adaptation scenario narrative of the island of New Providence against higher temperatures, heat stress and associated extremes. Source: BUUR PoS, 2024

5.2. Evaluation of the adaptation measures

Both the unsealing and greening adaptation scenario narratives have been evaluated for their effect on heat stress and temperatures for Nassau. In this analysis, we investigate the impacts on daily maximum temperature, minimum temperature and heat stress levels.

5.2.1. Modelling of adaptation options

Maximum temperatures are impacted by the amount of high vegetation that is present in the city, as trees offer evaporative cooling, leading to lower temperatures. This is reflected in the Figure 45 below. Although there is little space in the city of Nassau for planting trees, the areas where high vegetation is added offer cooling up to 0.5°C. However, the effects of the cooling are very local, mainly through the fact that the extent of the tree planting is very small.

Figure 45. Daily annual average maximum temperature at present time for a) present land use, b) the greening scenario, and c) the difference between both. Source: VITO

Unsealing showed to have limited effects on daytime temperatures. However, it substantially affects the nighttime urban heat island. Less sealed surfaces lead to less heat storage during the day and less heat release during the night. This is reflected in Figure 46 below, where we see a widespread cooling effect not only over the urban areas that are unsealed, but also propagating over the rest of the island.

Figure 46. Daily annual average minimum temperature at present time for a) present land use, b) the unsealing scenario, and c) the difference between both. Source: VITO

Interestingly, trees have a warming effect during the night. Cooling at night is prohibited more by the canopy of the trees compared to open surfaces, leading to (slightly) higher temperatures during the night in forests compared to open areas, where radiative cooling is easier (Beele et al., 2024).

When looking at heat stress values (considering temperatures, humidity and radiation), more distinct impacts become visible. Both the unsealing and the greening adaptation scenario provide substantial benefits to heat stress experienced by humans on the island, mainly driven by on the one hand lower radiation from unsealed surfaces and extra shade that is provided by the trees. This is reflected in Figure 47 below, showcasing a substantial decrease in heat stress experienced by humans over the island when unsealing the city by as little as 20 %. Highest decreases are again observed where unsealing took place, but again, positive benefits propagate to other areas. A decrease in days with high heat stress up to 30 % is achieved.

Figure 47. Number of days with high heat stress levels at present day a) with present land use, b) unsealing adaptation scenario, and c) the difference between the two. Source: VITO

Nevertheless, climate change will substantially increase the number of days with high heat stress. By 2050, under the high emission SSP5-8.5 scenario, the number of days with high heat stress will increase by 50-60 % (Figure 48). The positive benefits of unsealing will still lower the number of heat stress days (although less efficient in a warmer climate, compare Figure 47 c) and Figure 48 c), but numbers will still be higher than in a present-day climate without any adaptation. This clearly showcases the limits to adaptation and the need for mitigation efforts next to adaptation.

Figure 48. Number of days with high heat stress levels in 2050 under the SSP5-8.5 scenario with a) present land use, b) unsealing adaptation scenario, and c) the difference between the two. Source: VITO

5.2.2. Impacts of adaptation options

For the two adaptation options modelled for which daily maximal temperature, daily minimal temperatures, and heat stress days were discussed, the change in impact on people was assessed for the current climate and future pathways (SSP585, SSP534-over and SSP119). The population density distribution is considered static as in 2020. The highest heatwave warning level for New Providence based on the maximal daily temperatures is used to determine the number of people affected by extreme daily heat. The empirical sleep-loss function of minimal temperature derived by Minor et al. (2022) is used to determine the cumulative long-term health impact of lack of sleep. For details on the methodology see PROVIDE-report D4.2. As shown on the top row in Figure 49 below, adaptation options reduce the daily and nightly heat impacts on people to varying degrees.

Figure 49.
Top: Change in heat impacts on people (orange) for heatwave warnings (a), extreme heat stress (b) and loss of sleep (c) along the delayed action overshoot pathway (at global temperature overshoot peak in 2061-2070 and end of century 2081-2090) and the effect of unsealing (green) and greening (purple) cumulated for the whole island of New Providence.
Bottom: Change in heat impacts with unsealing and greening for each location in the New Providence with a population of at least 5 people per 100m². Note that changes below 1% are considered within the uncertainty of the UrbClim model. Source: VITO

Under the *Delayed Climate Action* overshoot pathway, the unsealing and park system adaptation yield contrasting effects during the day and the night. While unsealing can offset most of the increase in impacts from climate change for the reduction in sleep, it overall increases the number of people affected by daily maximum heat. This is because unsealing mostly reduces radiation, and thus is useful in decreasing heat stress (wet bulb globe temperature). However, maximum temperatures might increase slightly due to a decrease in terrain roughness, and thus lead to an increase in people warning days. The park system contributes to reducing daily maximum temperatures, but only slightly reduces the impact on people, as trees can mostly be planted in low population density areas. Furthermore, trees can store heat from the day preventing temperatures from

decreasing at night. Overall, however, the reduction in sleep loss is negligible (within the UrbClim model uncertainty).

The picture becomes more differentiated when looking at the impact at each location as shown on the bottom of Figure 49. Unsealing reduces strongly heat stress in urban areas, and sleep loss in the whole region. The greening strongly reduces heat stress overall and helps with heat warnings in the more urban areas.

5.3. Implementation strategies and next steps

A virtual workshop targeting national stakeholders was held to discuss adaptation planning, showcase the results of climate impacts modelling for heat stress and tropical cyclones, provide adaptation narratives to heat stress and flooding, and quantify the potential and limits of selected adaptation measures to address heat stress. Presentations were done by PROVIDE consortium partners, and a Miro board showcasing potential adaptation narratives to address impacts from heat and tropical cyclones, along with a generic portfolio of adaptation measures addressing heat stress and flooding, was distributed to participants.

The local participants, representing national government, private sector, and national universities, highlighted the need for adaptation portfolios and appreciated the development of generic adaptation portfolios to generate discussion and contribute to the national adaptation plan which is under development. Opportunities for implementation were noted for greening initiatives, and architectural initiatives including cool reflective materials and increasing ventilating and shading of existing and new buildings. Moreover, the need for culturally contextual adaptation options was highlighted, particularly for measures to address flooding risk. The potential for maladaptation in a multi-hazard context was discussed, as measures that were shown to be beneficial to address negative impacts of one hazard could exacerbate the impacts of another. Furthermore, the need for education and awareness, and the involvement multiple actors, including private sector for uptake of measures was indicated. Overall, finance was emphasized as a major barrier to implementation, as well as lack of adherence to existing laws and building codes. The Office of the Prime Minister, which is responsible for the climate change portfolio for The Bahamas, has indicated keen interest in continued work with PROVIDE-partners based on the outcome of this workshop.

6. Concluding remarks

This report presents the efforts within the PROVIDE project to co-develop overshoot adaptation scenario narratives and high-resolution maps in its four iconic cities and iconic regions around the world: Lisbon Metropolitan Area, Portugal, Iberian Mediterranean; Islamabad, Pakistan, Upper Indus Basin; Bodø, Norway, Arctic Fennoscandia; and Nassau, The Bahamas, Small Island region. The co-development of adaptation scenario narratives together with local stakeholders and interested parties has been the basis for the testing of adaptation strategies, options and concrete measures, using modelling that was finally reported in high-resolution maps.

The results from working with local stakeholders and with local adaptation plans is that even the more general policy recommendations, such as increasing the number of trees or make sure to keep natural water catchment areas in the urban fabric can result in significant contributions to decrease negative impacts from high temperatures or heavy precipitation, if they are properly implemented and put to practice. Moreover, we show examples of how the adaptation measures that we suggest can be closely related to already existing adaptation strategies in order to make them more practically feasible.

In the **Lisbon Metropolitan Area**, we have proposed several measures and recommendations that are closely related to already existing adaptation strategies proposed by the Metropolitan Area's plan for adaptation (PMACC-AML). Increasing the number of trees and unsealing are adaptation measures that can make significant contributions to decrease heat stress and maximum temperatures, in urban centres and peri-urban areas. Yet, the cooling measures are impacted by climate change themselves (e.g., tree plantation) and do not necessarily allow for future reverse adaptation. In that regard, a strategy of unsealing build surfaces is essential in allowing built-in flexibility to adaptation under overshoot scenarios. Moreover, there are many specific regulatory jurisdictions in the Lisbon Metropolitan Area municipalities which can restrict the type of intervention or adaptation measure that can be implemented and in which area. However, there are also many ongoing initiatives that can be supported with the results and recommendations from PROVIDE.

In **Islamabad**, the cost-effective and implementable recommendations to improve infrastructure and expand urban green spaces (afforestation) and water management sectors in this report are in line with the existing national adaptation policies. The proposed adaptation scenario narratives for sector E-11 are mainly incorporating nature-based solutions consistent with core focus of the current climate change and developmental policies as well as ongoing projects. Although there are synergies with existing national policies, there is a need to develop context-specific, climate-smart urban plans in more sectors of Islamabad, which must be tailored to the local needs of the communities. Most importantly, the suggested adaptation needs must be integrated into the long-term development planning and not be treated as passing seasonal challenges to avoid adverse consequences and allow for future reverse adaptation. Furthermore, the development plans must be inclusive and leave no one behind. Challenges range from the unaffordability of cooling mechanisms to the nature of outdoor work that exposes individuals to extreme heat for extended periods of time. Such limitations are often overlooked in policy documents and city planning.

In **Bodø**, there is a high level of adaptation capacity but there is also uncertainty about future climate impacts and the need to plan and invest accordingly. For example, the preservation of existing agricultural and arable land depends on the position of the prevailing local political regime. All the proposed adaptation measures in this report depends on committed investments, long-term planning, and political will to be

implemented. Preserving arable land, unsealing asphalted areas, and keeping natural streams open are all measures to avoid negative impacts from more precipitation and allow for nature-based adaptation. Overall, we see a need to contribute locally with more knowledge and awareness of current and future climate change impacts, as well as current and future adaptation options.

In **Nassau**, the local stakeholders stress the need for adaptation portfolios to contribute to the national adaptation plan that is underway. This includes the adaptation scenario narrative measures of greening the city as well as building with more cool reflective materials and increase shading and ventilation. However, as in the other cases, a major barrier for implementing adaptation measures is the finance as well as lack of adherence to existing laws and building codes. There is also a need for more knowledge and education as well as involvement of multiple actors in the adaptation work, including the private sector. Positively, the leadership in The Bahamas are interested in further collaboration to increase adaptive capacity and the implementation of additional adaptation measures.

Overall, our findings show that:

- Thinking, working and planning under various climate scenarios have gained prominence in recent years, although the topic of overshoot has yet to become a widely established term within local adaptation planning in the four iconic cities.
- Potential overshoot scenarios across long-term horizons are the most relevant for long-term adaptation planning and to a large degree involved urban infrastructure-based measures that must be planned today.
- It is essential to involve local stakeholders as well as a plethora of knowledges from various disciplines, including urban planners, to build capacity to design science-based adaptation plans that support long-term effectiveness and avoid maladaptation.
- All the proposed adaptation measures in all the four Iconic cities require committed investments and political will to be implemented.
- It is essential that both local stakeholders, adaptation planners, politicians and the public are aware of current and future climate change impacts and the effects of, for example, infrastructure decisions and constructions made today.
- Urban design can both increase resilience and adaptation capacity as well as the overall quality of life for urban residents under climate change scenarios.
- Possibilities as well as limits to adaptation and reversibility of local climate change impacts must relate to the specificity of local urban challenges and possible nature-based solutions.
- The more locally applicable and detailed the science-based inputs are (e.g. adaptation hotspots, high-resolution impact maps, locally anchored adaptation measures), the more relevant it is for local adaptation practitioners.

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Links to the two PROVIDE-reports that this report builds on:

[PROVIDE_NRI_D4.1_Review-Reports.pdf \(provide-h2020.eu\)](#)

[PROVIDE_D4.2-Four-Overshoot-Proofing-reports-FINAL-21122023_5.pdf \(provide-h2020.eu\)](#)

Annex 1: Catalogue of measures for adaptation to heat stress¹⁸

heat regulation

green infrastructure

A.1

Green ventilation corridors (vegetated verges)

Delft 2009 © Andre, source: <https://urbangreenbluegrids.com/measures/green-ventilation-grids/>

Evaluation Matrix

cooling

evapotranspiration/shading

heat regulation

green infrastructure

heat regulation

green infrastructure

[DESCRIPTION] Green ventilation grids are linear green spaces that are strategically located to facilitate the flow of cool air into the city. They are integrated into the urban infrastructure, such as along roads or railways, to provide a cooling effect. // **[PRINCIPLES]** Green areas are connected in such a way that a continuous line of green space is created: a corridor design of interconnected half-open areas for optimal airflow, and a not too high vegetation density. // **[CHALLENGES]** The main challenges to the implementation of green grids include the limited availability of land, the need for ongoing maintenance, and the potential for conflicts with other urban functions (e.g. transportation and utility infrastructure).

Co-benefits

Biodiversity	■ ■ ■	Health	■ ■ ■ ■
Air quality	■ ■ ■	Education	■ ■ ■
Cultural importance & social interaction	■ ■ ■	Multifunctional use of space	■ ■ ■
Water	■ ■ ■	Tourism/Recreation	■ ■ ■
Energy	■ ■ ■	Resource production	■ ■ ■

Sectoral coalitions

agriculture/forestry	biodiversity
aquaculture	ecosystems
urbanized landscape	water reserves
amenities	energy systems
industry	mobility infrastructure
recreation/tourism	transport

cooling

evapotranspiration/shading

heat regulation

green infrastructure

A.2

Areas of ecological value (ecosystem restoration)

Amar Sjauw En Wa, source: <https://urbangreenbluegrids.com/measures/creating-maintaining-and-improving-green-areas-and-unhardening-surfaces/>

Evaluation Matrix

cooling

evapotranspiration/shading

[DESCRIPTION] Creating areas of ecological value and ecosystem protection and restoration are nature-based solutions for urban cooling that help to reduce the urban heat island effect and provide additional benefits such as improved air quality and increased biodiversity. // **[PRINCIPLES]** The basic principles for designing these measures include identifying areas with high ecological value, and protecting and restoring natural habitats, by incorporating spatial variation to the design and allowing linkages within the larger landscape. // **[CHALLENGES]** Challenges to implementing these measures include engaging with stakeholders to ensure that these measures are supported and maintained over the long term.

Co-benefits

Biodiversity	■ ■ ■ ■	Health	■ ■ ■ ■
Air quality	■ ■ ■ ■	Education	■ ■ ■
Cultural importance & social interaction	■ ■ ■	Multifunctional use of space	■ ■ ■
Water	■ ■ ■ ■	Tourism/Recreation	■ ■ ■
Energy	■ ■ ■	Resource production	■ ■ ■

Sectoral coalitions

agriculture/forestry	biodiversity
aquaculture	ecosystems
urbanized landscape	water reserves
amenities	energy systems
industry	mobility infrastructure
recreation/tourism	transport

cooling

evapotranspiration/shading

¹⁸ Developed by the PROVIDE-consortium team from BUUR Part of Sweco.

heat regulation

green infrastructure

A.3 Green-riparian zones (ecological corridors)

Brasserhout, Den Haag, The Netherlands, source: <https://urbangreenbluegrids.com/measures/green-riparian-zones-and-wet-biotopes/>

Evaluation Matrix

cooling

evapotranspiration/shading

heat regulation

green infrastructure

heat regulation

green infrastructure

[DESCRIPTION] Green-riparian zones and ecological corridors are nature-based solutions for urban cooling that involve creating green spaces along waterways and other natural features in the urban environment // **[PRINCIPLES]** The basic principles for designing green-riparian zones and ecological corridors include selecting appropriate plant species, ensuring adequate soil quality, providing irrigation, and designing for a zone of minimum of 6 meters. // **[CHALLENGES]** Challenges include land availability, maintenance, conflicts with other urban functions, funding, and integrating them within urban planning. Lack of coordination and inadequate regulations further complicate their design and implementation.

Co-benefits

Biodiversity	■ ■ ■	Health	■ ■ ■
Air quality	■	Education	■
Cultural importance & social interaction	■ ■	Multifunctional use of space	■
Water	■ ■	Tourism/Recreation	■ ■
Energy	■ ■	Resource production	■

Sectoral coalitions

- | | |
|----------------------|-------------------------|
| agriculture/forestry | biodiversity |
| aquaculture | ecosystems |
| urbanized landscape | water reserves |
| amenities | energy systems |
| industry | mobility infrastructure |
| recreation/tourism | transport |

cooling

evapotranspiration/shading

heat regulation

green infrastructure

A.4 Urban forests and Parks

Urban forest, source: <https://urbangreenbluegrids.com/measures/urban-forests/>

Evaluation Matrix

cooling

evapotranspiration/shading

heat regulation

green infrastructure

[DESCRIPTION] Forests and parks are nature-based solutions for urban cooling that involve the strategic planting and maintenance of mixed forests with open areas that meet various social demands, and can also produce biomass. // **[PRINCIPLES]** When designing urban forests and parks, the proximity to other urban functions should enable air purification while retaining sufficient open space for urban ventilation and heat stress alleviation. Surface area of at least 200m² for parks and 2.5 hectares for forests is recommended. // **[CHALLENGES]** Urban trees are constantly exposed to pollutants, high temperatures, drought, and inundation. Limited resources often hinder proper maintenance.

Co-benefits

Biodiversity	■ ■ ■	Health	■ ■ ■
Air quality	■ ■	Education	■ ■
Cultural importance & social interaction	■ ■ ■	Multifunctional use of space	■ ■ ■
Water	■ ■ ■	Tourism/Recreation	■ ■ ■
Energy	■ ■	Resource production	■

Sectoral coalitions

- | | |
|----------------------|-------------------------|
| agriculture/forestry | biodiversity |
| aquaculture | ecosystems |
| urbanized landscape | water reserves |
| amenities | energy systems |
| industry | mobility infrastructure |
| recreation/tourism | transport |

cooling

evapotranspiration/shading

heat regulation

green infrastructure

A.5 Green avenues and tree-lined streets

Trees in Prague, source: <https://urbangreenbluegrids.com/measures/street-trees-and-tree-lined-lanes/>

Evaluation Matrix

cooling

evapotranspiration/shading

heat regulation

green infrastructure

heat regulation

green infrastructure

[DESCRIPTION] Green avenues are nature-based solutions for urban cooling that involve the creation of linear green spaces that are aligned with the direction of prevailing winds to facilitate the flow of cool air into the city. // **[PRINCIPLES]** Design principles include ensuring adequate soil quality, providing irrigation and maintenance, and integrating them into urban planning. Further, the design of green avenues should follow the principles compact and poly-centric cities. // **[CHALLENGES]** Challenges to implementing green avenues include limited land availability, conflicts with other urban functions such as transportation and utility infrastructure, and the need for ongoing maintenance.

Co-benefits

Biodiversity	■ ■ ■	Health	■ ■
Air quality	■ ■	Education	■
Cultural importance & social interaction	■ ■ ■	Multifunctional use of space	■
Water	■ ■	Tourism/Recreation	■
Energy	■	Resource production	■

Sectoral coalitions

agriculture/forestry	biodiversity
aquaculture	ecosystems
urbanized landscape	water reserves
amenities	energy systems
industry	mobility infrastructure
recreation/tourism	transport

cooling

evapotranspiration/shading

heat regulation

green infrastructure

A.6 Green squares and playgrounds

Marco Polo-Terrassen, source: <https://urbangreenbluegrids.com/measures/green-squares-and-playgrounds/>

Evaluation Matrix

cooling

evapotranspiration/shading

[DESCRIPTION] Green squares and playgrounds are nature-based solutions for urban cooling that involve the creation of green spaces within the urban environment, which provide refugia for wildlife, recreational and cultural programs, and amenities or urban communities. // **[PRINCIPLES]** Designs for squares and playgrounds can include a critical consideration of the proportion of paved areas: they tend to be semi-paved and bordered by trees that provide shade, while playgrounds can be covered with sand, tree bark or grass, and can also feature more trees and shrubs. // **[CHALLENGES]** Challenges to implementing these measures include the access to or ownership of land which is required for open green space in urban areas.

Co-benefits

Biodiversity	■ ■ ■	Health	■ ■
Air quality	■ ■	Education	■
Cultural importance & social interaction	■ ■ ■	Multifunctional use of space	■ ■
Water	■ ■ ■	Tourism/Recreation	■ ■
Energy	■	Resource production	■ ■

Sectoral coalitions

agriculture/forestry	biodiversity
aquaculture	ecosystems
urbanized landscape	water reserves
amenities	energy systems
industry	mobility infrastructure
recreation/tourism	transport

cooling

evapotranspiration/shading

heat regulation

green infrastructure

A.7 Green roofs and facades

Garden roof in Stuttgart, Germany, source: <https://urbangreenbluegrids.com/measures/green-roofs/>

Evaluation Matrix

cooling

evapotranspiration/shading

heat regulation

green infrastructure

heat regulation

green infrastructure

[DESCRIPTION] Green roofs and facades can help mitigate the urban heat island effect by providing shading and evapotranspiration. They are vegetated structures that consist of a waterproofing layer, growing medium, and vegetation. // **[PRINCIPLES]** The growing medium should have appropriate depth and composition for the plants to thrive, and irrigation systems should be provided to ensure adequate water supply. Depending on climate, choice of species, orientation and nutrition, they may take several seasons to achieve maturity. // **[CHALLENGES]** Except for high installation and maintenance costs, there may be structural limitations that prevent the installation of green roofs and facades on some buildings.

Co-benefits

Biodiversity	■ ■	Health	■
Air quality	■ ■	Education	■
Cultural importance & social interaction	■ ■	Multifunctional use of space	■ ■
Water	■ ■	Tourism/Recreation	■
Energy	■	Resource production	■

Sectoral coalitions

agriculture/forestry	biodiversity
aquaculture	ecosystems
urbanized landscape	water reserves
amenities	energy systems
industry	mobility infrastructure
recreation/tourism	transport

cooling

evapotranspiration/shading

heat regulation

green infrastructure

A.8 Urban farming

Hoeve Biesland farm near Delft, source: <https://urbangreenbluegrids.com/measures/commercial-initiatives/>

Evaluation Matrix

cooling

evapotranspiration/shading

[DESCRIPTION] Urban farming refers to the practice of cultivating crops and raising animals in urban areas, often in small-scale and community-based initiatives. // **[PRINCIPLES]** An urban farm requires consideration of factors such as location, soil quality, available space, and climate. The type of crops grown should be selected based on the local climate and soil conditions, and irrigation systems should be designed to conserve water. // **[CHALLENGES]** Challenges to implementing urban farming include limited access to land, lack of technical expertise, and high installation and maintenance costs. In addition, there may be regulatory barriers to urban farming, such as zoning and land-use regulations.

Co-benefits

Biodiversity	■	Health	■
Air quality	■	Education	■ ■
Cultural importance & social interaction	■ ■ ■	Multifunctional use of space	■ ■
Water	■ ■	Tourism/Recreation	■
Energy	■	Resource production	■ ■ ■

Sectoral coalitions

agriculture/forestry	biodiversity
aquaculture	ecosystems
urbanized landscape	water reserves
amenities	energy systems
industry	mobility infrastructure
recreation/tourism	transport

cooling

evapotranspiration/shading

heat regulation

green infrastructure

A.9
Private Gardens

- source: <https://urbangreenbluegrids.com/measures/reduce-paved-surfaces/>

Evaluation Matrix

cooling

evapotranspiration/shading

heat regulation

green infrastructure

heat regulation

green infrastructure

[DESCRIPTION] Non-public areas such as private gardens greatly influence the urban micro-climate and the perceived temperature. They can help mitigate the urban heat island effect by providing shading and evapotranspiration, as well as by reducing the amount of impervious surfaces in urban areas. // **[PRINCIPLES]** The selection of plants should be based on the local climate and soil conditions, and irrigation systems should be designed to conserve water. To maximize the cooling effect, plants with high shading and evapotranspiration rates should be selected. // **[CHALLENGES]** There may be cultural and behavioral barriers to gardening, such as a lack of interest or time, or, mainly, financial incentive.

Co-benefits

Biodiversity	■ ■	Health	■ ■
Air quality	■	Education	■
Cultural importance & social interaction	■ ■ ■	Multifunctional use of space	■ ■
Water	■ ■	Tourism/Recreation	■ ■ ■
Energy	■ ■	Resource production	■ ■ ■

Sectoral coalitions

- | | | | |
|--|----------------------|--|-------------------------|
| | agriculture/forestry | | biodiversity |
| | aquaculture | | ecosystems |
| | urbanized landscape | | water reserves |
| | amenities | | energy systems |
| | industry | | mobility infrastructure |
| | recreation/tourism | | transport |

cooling

evapotranspiration/shading

heat regulation

green infrastructure

A.10
Green industrial sites

Garden. source: <https://urbangreenbluegrids.com/measures/green-private-gardens/>

Evaluation Matrix

cooling

evapotranspiration/shading

[DESCRIPTION] Non-public areas such as private gardens and industrial sites greatly influence the urban micro-climate, the perceived temperature, and the control of the water mission. // **[PRINCIPLES]** Greening industrial sites takes, also, the role of cleaning polluted soils. As such, design principles for green industrial sites involve both ecological considerations, as well as the unique characteristics of the site and its function. // **[CHALLENGES]** Industrial sites are traditionally very paved. More education about the importance of greenery in the city can help offset this trend. Taxing paving can help in this regard, as can the introduction of urban planning strategies and policies.

Co-benefits

Biodiversity	■ ■	Health	■
Air quality	■	Education	■
Cultural importance & social interaction	■ ■ ■	Multifunctional use of space	■ ■
Water	■ ■	Tourism/Recreation	■ ■ ■
Energy	■ ■	Resource production	■

Sectoral coalitions

- | | | | |
|--|----------------------|--|-------------------------|
| | agriculture/forestry | | biodiversity |
| | aquaculture | | ecosystems |
| | urbanized landscape | | water reserves |
| | amenities | | energy systems |
| | industry | | mobility infrastructure |
| | recreation/tourism | | transport |

cooling

evapotranspiration/shading

heat regulation

green infrastructure

A.11

Green car parks

Groene parkeerplaats in Frankrijk, source: <https://urbangreenbluegrids.com/measures/car-parks-with-green-areas/>

Evaluation Matrix

cooling

evapotranspiration/shading

heat regulation

green infrastructure

heat regulation

green infrastructure

[DESCRIPTION] Car parks that see less intensive use can be paved with surfacing open to vegetation and be planted with trees. These car parks can serve as cool islands in the town or city, industrial estates, harbours and business estates are some of the hottest urban areas. // **[PRINCIPLES]** Planting trees on semi-paved car parks would be one way to lower temperatures. An additional benefit is that the cars underneath a tree canopy will also stay cooler inside and that the trees will purify from the air some of the emissions generated by the cars. // **[CHALLENGES]** Challenges for green parking areas include installation costs, lack of incentive, and technical issues with installing permeable pavements.

Co-benefits

Biodiversity	■ ■	Health	■
Air quality	■	Education	
Cultural importance & social interaction	■ ■ ■	Multifunctional use of space	■ ■
Water	■ ■	Tourism/Recreation	
Energy	■ ■	Resource production	

Sectoral coalitions

- | | | | |
|--|----------------------|--|-------------------------|
| | agriculture/forestry | | biodiversity |
| | aquaculture | | ecosystems |
| | urbanized landscape | | water reserves |
| | amenities | | energy systems |
| | industry | | mobility infrastructure |
| | recreation/tourism | | transport |

cooling

evapotranspiration/shading

heat regulation

green infrastructure

A.12

Individual trees

Blossom, Source: atelier GROENBLAUW, Monique Hoogland

Evaluation Matrix

cooling

evapotranspiration/shading

[DESCRIPTION] Trees are the most effective cooling measure because they not only provide shade but also help cool the air through evaporation. // **[PRINCIPLES]** It is important to consider the space it will grow in, to be sure that it will have enough room to fully develop its crown and roots. In consultation with residents, placing more fruit-bearing trees can enrich a cityscape. // **[CHALLENGES]** More drought-tolerant species offer more cooling through evaporation than less drought-tolerant species. Trees need room to grow and flourish, both above and below ground. A poor selection of species in terms of the adult size of the tree, can lead to conflicts with the surrounding infrastructure. Similarly, water requirements should be met.

Co-benefits

Biodiversity	■ ■ ■	Health	■ ■ ■
Air quality	■	Education	■
Cultural importance & social interaction	■ ■ ■	Multifunctional use of space	■ ■
Water	■ ■	Tourism/Recreation	■
Energy	■	Resource production	■

Sectoral coalitions

- | | | | |
|--|----------------------|--|-------------------------|
| | agriculture/forestry | | biodiversity |
| | aquaculture | | ecosystems |
| | urbanized landscape | | water reserves |
| | amenities | | energy systems |
| | industry | | mobility infrastructure |
| | recreation/tourism | | transport |

cooling

evapotranspiration/shading

heat regulation

green infrastructure

A.13
Soil unsealing (planted/permeable surfaces, lawns)

- source: <https://urbangreenbluegrids.com/measures/reduce-paved-surfaces/>

Evaluation Matrix

cooling

evapotranspiration/shading

heat regulation

blue infrastructure

heat regulation

green infrastructure

[DESCRIPTION] Removing paving creates more room for plantings and the plants keep the area cooler on hot summer days. It also offers animals, plants and soil life more space. // **[PRINCIPLES]** Indigenous species are suited for the particular type of measure. // **[CHALLENGES]** Challenges to implementing this measure include cost (especially in densely populated areas where land is at a premium), logistics (careful planning and coordination to ensure that the work is done safely and efficiently), maintenance (ongoing maintenance to ensure that the vegetation remains healthy and that the soil remains permeable), and public perception (some members of the public prefer traditional paved surfaces).

Co-benefits

Biodiversity	■ ■	Health	■
Air quality	■	Education	■
Cultural importance & social interaction	■ ■	Multifunctional use of space	■ ■
Water	■ ■ ■	Tourism/Recreation	■ ■
Energy	■	Resource production	■

Sectoral coalitions

- agriculture/forestry
- biodiversity
- aquaculture
- ecosystems
- urbanized landscape
- water reserves
- amenities
- energy systems
- industry
- mobility infrastructure
- recreation/tourism
- transport

cooling

evapotranspiration/shading

heat regulation

blue infrastructure

B.1
Stream naturalization (riparian zone restoration)

Brasserhout, Den Haag, The Netherlands, source: <https://urbangreenbluegrids.com/measures/green-riparian-zones-and-wet-biotopes/>

Evaluation Matrix

cooling

evaporation

[DESCRIPTION] This approach involves restoring or enhancing the natural characteristics of streams and rivers that have been modified or degraded by human activities. // **[PRINCIPLES]** Stream and river (re-)naturalization requires consideration of factors such as the location of the watercourse, the surrounding land use, and the hydrological conditions. The restoration should aim to create a more natural and diverse habitat, with a variety of vegetation types and water features. This can include meanders, pools, riffles, and wetlands. // **[CHALLENGES]** Challenges include the need for significant technical expertise and potential conflicts with other land uses.

Co-benefits

Biodiversity	■ ■ ■	Health	■ ■ ■
Air quality	■	Education	■
Cultural importance & social interaction	■ ■	Multifunctional use of space	■
Water	■ ■	Tourism/Recreation	■
Energy	■ ■	Resource production	■

Sectoral coalitions

- agriculture/forestry
- biodiversity
- aquaculture
- ecosystems
- urbanized landscape
- water reserves
- amenities
- energy systems
- industry
- mobility infrastructure
- recreation/tourism
- transport

cooling

evaporation

heat regulation

blue infrastructure

B.2 Surface water plan

Evaluation Matrix

cooling

evaporation

heat regulation

blue infrastructure

heat regulation

blue infrastructure

[DESCRIPTION] Surface water planning uses water bodies to cool urban areas, by restoring and protecting natural water bodies, or creating new ones. // **[PRINCIPLES]** When designing surface water planning measures for urban cooling, it is important to maximize the surface area of water bodies (the more water surface area there is, the more heat can be absorbed and evaporated) and design urban areas to allow for the natural flow of water (this helps to distribute the cooling effect of water throughout the city). // **[CHALLENGES]** Challenges to implementing surface water planning as a nature-based solution include the need for significant technical expertise and potential conflicts with other land uses.

Co-benefits

Biodiversity	■ ■ ■	Health	■ ■ ■ ■
Air quality	■	Education	■ ■
Cultural importance & social interaction	■ ■ ■	Multifunctional use of space	■ ■
Water	■ ■ ■	Tourism/Recreation	■ ■
Energy	■ ■	Resource production	■

Sectoral coalitions

- | | |
|----------------------|-------------------------|
| agriculture/forestry | biodiversity |
| aquaculture | ecosystems |
| urbanized landscape | water reserves |
| amenities | energy systems |
| industry | mobility infrastructure |
| recreation/tourism | transport |

cooling

evaporation

heat regulation

blue infrastructure

B.3 Fountains

pxhere, source: <https://urbangreenbluegrids.com/measures/reducing-heat-with-water/>

Evaluation Matrix

cooling

evaporation

[DESCRIPTION] Bringing people into contact with water is an effective way to reduce heat stress through its evaporation (on the skin) or through a moist air flow that has been cooled: evaporated water leads to an actual temperature decrease of the air temperature. // **[PRINCIPLES]** Fountains provide cooling through evaporation: because many small water droplets have a relatively larger contact surface with the air than one flat water surface, there is more evaporation (the smaller the droplets, the more evaporation and the more efficient the cooling of the air). // **[CHALLENGES]** The extent to which the cooling effect extends also depends on wind speed and direction.

Co-benefits

Biodiversity	■ ■	Health	■ ■ ■
Air quality	■	Education	■
Cultural importance & social interaction	■ ■	Multifunctional use of space	■
Water	■ ■	Tourism/Recreation	■
Energy		Resource production	

Sectoral coalitions

- | | |
|----------------------|-------------------------|
| agriculture/forestry | biodiversity |
| aquaculture | ecosystems |
| urbanized landscape | water reserves |
| amenities | energy systems |
| industry | mobility infrastructure |
| recreation/tourism | transport |

cooling

evaporation

heat regulation

blue infrastructure

B.4 Sprinklers/Foggers

Irrigation by a sprinkler. source: <https://urbangreenbluegrids.com/measures/smart-irrigation-measures/>

Evaluation Matrix

cooling

evaporation

heat regulation

blue infrastructure

heat regulation

blue infrastructure

[DESCRIPTION] Nebulization of water can provide cooling in two ways thanks to the many small water droplets that ensure that the contact surface with the air is large. Also, the water mist cools the skin because the droplets moisten it and extract heat from it through evaporation. // **[PRINCIPLES]** It is especially effective in combination with a fan, because wind accelerates the heat exchange between wet skin and the environment. // **[CHALLENGES]** The cooling effect is short-lived. This measure is mainly applied in Mediterranean countries.

Co-benefits

Biodiversity	Health
Air quality	Education
Cultural importance & social interaction	Multifunctional use of space
Water	Tourism/Recreation
Energy	Resource production

Sectoral coalitions

- agriculture/forestry
- aquaculture
- urbanized landscape
- amenities
- industry
- recreation/tourism
- biodiversity
- ecosystems
- water reserves
- energy systems
- mobility infrastructure
- transport

cooling

evaporation

heat regulation

blue infrastructure

B.5 Watering

Evaluation Matrix

cooling

evaporation

[DESCRIPTION] By wetting streets, the air temperature can drop by 0.8 to 3°C. At a height of 2 meters on a wet street can drop by a maximum of 2°C, and this can reduce the surface temperature of the street by up to 13°C. Wetting the street also ensures that less solar radiation is reflected (the albedo decreases). This also reduces the perceived temperature for pedestrians and cyclists on the road. // **[PRINCIPLES]** // **[CHALLENGES]** A side note is that the evaporation of the water can increase the humidity. Wetting streets can also have a negative effect on the perceived temperature.

Co-benefits

Biodiversity	Health
Air quality	Education
Cultural importance & social interaction	Multifunctional use of space
Water	Tourism/Recreation
Energy	Resource production

Sectoral coalitions

- agriculture/forestry
- aquaculture
- urbanized landscape
- amenities
- industry
- recreation/tourism
- biodiversity
- ecosystems
- water reserves
- energy systems
- mobility infrastructure
- transport

cooling

evaporation

heat regulation

agriculture adaptation

C.1
Agroforestry

Evaluation Matrix

protection

resistance

heat regulation

agriculture adaptation

heat regulation

agriculture adaptation

[DESCRIPTION] Agroforestry integrates trees and shrubs into crop and livestock production systems, and can help to adapt to heat stress through: providing shade and cooling the air, reducing soil and air temperatures, increasing soil moisture and reducing evaporation, and improving wind protection. // **[PRINCIPLES]** It is important to consider the following: right tree and shrub species (that are adapted to the local climate and soil conditions, and provide the desired benefits), and design the system for optimal shade and wind protection. // **[CHALLENGES]** Some of the challenges to implementing agroforestry systems include: insecure land tenure, lack of knowledge and technical expertise, and lack of financial support

Co-benefits

Biodiversity	■ ■	Health	■ ■
Air quality	■	Education	■
Cultural importance & social interaction	■	Multifunctional use of space	■ ■ ■
Water	■ ■	Tourism/Recreation	■
Energy	■	Resource production	■ ■ ■

Sectoral coalitions

- 🌾 agriculture/forestry
- 🌱 biodiversity
- 🐟 aquaculture
- 🌿 ecosystems
- 🏙️ urbanized landscape
- 💧 water reserves
- 🏡 amenities
- ⚡ energy systems
- 🏭 industry
- 🚗 mobility infrastructure
- 🎒 recreation/tourism
- 🚗 transport

protection

resistance

heat regulation

agriculture adaptation

C.2
Farming diversification and new crops

Evaluation Matrix

protection

resistance

[DESCRIPTION] Crop diversification involves growing a variety of different crops on the same farm, and can help to adapt to heat stress through: reducing the risk of crop failure, and thanks to the fact that diversified cropping systems tend to have healthier soils, which can be more resilient to heat stress. // **[PRINCIPLES]** It is important to consider the following: select a variety of crops with different heat tolerances, and include crops that provide ground cover (to reduce soil temperatures and evaporation). // **[CHALLENGES]** Some of the challenges include: farmers may not have access to markets for all of the crops that they produce, and diversified cropping systems can be more labor-intensive than monocultures.

Co-benefits

Biodiversity	■ ■	Health	■ ■
Air quality	■	Education	■
Cultural importance & social interaction	■	Multifunctional use of space	■
Water	■ ■	Tourism/Recreation	■
Energy	■	Resource production	■ ■ ■

Sectoral coalitions

- 🌾 agriculture/forestry
- 🌱 biodiversity
- 🐟 aquaculture
- 🌿 ecosystems
- 🏙️ urbanized landscape
- 💧 water reserves
- 🏡 amenities
- ⚡ energy systems
- 🏭 industry
- 🚗 mobility infrastructure
- 🎒 recreation/tourism
- 🚗 transport

protection

resistance

heat regulation

agriculture adaptation

C.3
Irrigation

Evaluation Matrix

protection

resistance

heat regulation

agriculture adaptation

heat regulation

agriculture adaptation

[DESCRIPTION] Irrigation can help to adapt agriculture to heat stress through: providing water to crops during periods of drought or high temperatures, cooling the air and soil around crops, and reducing evapotranspiration, which can help to conserve water // **[PRINCIPLES]** It is important to consider the following: use water-efficient irrigation methods (e.g. drip irrigation and sprinkler irrigation), irrigate at the right time, irrigate the right amount, and use water from sustainable sources (e.g. harvested rainwater or recycled water). // **[CHALLENGES]** Some of the challenges include: cost, water availability, energy requirements, and salinity.

Co-benefits

Biodiversity	■	Health	■ ■
Air quality		Education	■
Cultural importance & social interaction		Multifunctional use of space	
Water	■ ■ ■	Tourism/Recreation	
Energy	■	Resource production	■ ■ ■

Sectoral coalitions

- | | |
|----------------------|-------------------------|
| agriculture/forestry | biodiversity |
| aquaculture | ecosystems |
| urbanized landscape | water reserves |
| amenities | energy systems |
| industry | mobility infrastructure |
| recreation/tourism | transport |

protection

resistance

heat regulation

agriculture adaptation

C.4
Multifunctional farming

Evaluation Matrix

protection

resistance

[DESCRIPTION] Multifunctional farming is an approach to agriculture that aims to produce food and other products while also providing environmental benefits, such as carbon sequestration, water quality improvement, and biodiversity enhancement, and even energy production. // **[PRINCIPLES]** It is important to consider the following: integrate a variety of farming practices, and consider the needs of the local community. // **[CHALLENGES]** Some of the challenges to implementing multifunctional farming systems for adaptation to heat stress include: cost (may require more investment than conventional farming systems), knowledge and technical expertise, and legal planning conflicts between the different uses and covers envisioned.

Co-benefits

Biodiversity	■	Health	
Air quality		Education	■
Cultural importance & social interaction	■	Multifunctional use of space	■ ■ ■
Water	■	Tourism/Recreation	■
Energy	■	Resource production	■ ■ ■

Sectoral coalitions

- | | |
|----------------------|-------------------------|
| agriculture/forestry | biodiversity |
| aquaculture | ecosystems |
| urbanized landscape | water reserves |
| amenities | energy systems |
| industry | mobility infrastructure |
| recreation/tourism | transport |

protection

resistance

heat regulation

agriculture adaptation

C.5
Indoor farming

pxhere, source: <https://urbangreenbluegrids.com/measures/reducing-heat-with-water/>

Evaluation Matrix

protection

resistance

heat regulation

structural/material adaptation

heat regulation

agriculture adaptation

[DESCRIPTION] Growing crops in controlled environments (e.g. greenhouses, warehouses, and shipping containers) can be beneficial for crop growth and yield and can help to adapt agriculture to heat stress through: reducing water use and the use of pesticides and fertilizers, and increasing the year-round availability of fresh produce. // **[PRINCIPLES]** It is important to consider the following principles: use energy- and water-efficient technologies, use integrated pest management (IPM) practices, and consider the needs of the local community. // **[CHALLENGES]** Some of the challenges to implementing include: cost (particularly energy costs), and access to land (which can be expensive and difficult to obtain in urban areas).

Co-benefits

Biodiversity	■	Health	■ ■
Air quality		Education	■
Cultural importance & social interaction	■	Multifunctional use of space	■ ■ ■
Water	■ ■ ■	Tourism/Recreation	■
Energy	■	Resource production	■ ■ ■

Sectoral coalitions

- agriculture/forestry
- aquaculture
- urbanized landscape
- amenities
- industry
- recreation/tourism
- biodiversity
- ecosystems
- water reserves
- energy systems
- mobility infrastructure
- transport

protection

resistance

D.1
Cool/Reflective materials

Wit dak, source: <https://groenblauwenetwerken.nl/measures/koele-daken/>

Evaluation Matrix

protection

resistance

[DESCRIPTION] Materials that reflect or absorb very little sunlight, help to keep surfaces cool and can be used to reduce heat stress through: reducing the temperature of buildings and other surfaces, shading people and objects, and reducing the urban heat island effect. // **[PRINCIPLES]** It is important to consider the following: select the right materials, design for optimal performance, and consider the needs of the community (e.g. cool roofs can be installed on public buildings and schools). // **[CHALLENGES]** Some of the challenges include: cost, lack of awareness, and lack of policies and incentives (primarily financial) to encourage the use of cool and/or reflective materials.

Co-benefits

Biodiversity		Health	■
Air quality		Education	
Cultural importance & social interaction		Multifunctional use of space	
Water		Tourism/Recreation	
Energy	■ ■	Resource production	

Sectoral coalitions

- agriculture/forestry
- aquaculture
- urbanized landscape
- amenities
- industry
- recreation/tourism
- biodiversity
- ecosystems
- water reserves
- energy systems
- mobility infrastructure
- transport

heat regulation

structural/material adaptation

D.2 Urban shadow facilities

Arcade, source: <https://groenblauwenetwerken.nl/measures/stedenbouwkundige-schaduwvoorzieningen/>

Evaluation Matrix

cooling

shading/ventilation

heat regulation

structural/material adaptation

heat regulation

structural/material adaptation

[DESCRIPTION] Facilities that provide shade and cooling in urban areas (e.g. buildings with awnings and overhangs) can help to reduce risk of heat exhaustion and stroke. // **[PRINCIPLES]** It is important to consider the following: locate facilities where they will be most beneficial (areas where people are most likely to be exposed to heat stress, such as public squares, playgrounds, and bus stops), and the needs of the community (they should be designed to be accessible and inclusive for all). // **[CHALLENGES]** Some of the challenges: cost, space (densely populated areas can make it difficult to find space for urban shadow facilities), and competing priorities: Urban planners and policymakers may have other competing priorities.

Co-benefits

Biodiversity	Health	■ ■
Air quality	Education	■
Cultural importance & social interaction	Multifunctional use of space	■ ■ ■ ■
Water	Tourism/Recreation	■ ■ ■ ■
Energy	Resource production	■

Sectoral coalitions

- agriculture/forestry
- aquaculture
- urbanized landscape
- amenities
- industry
- recreation/tourism
- biodiversity
- ecosystems
- water reserves
- energy systems
- mobility infrastructure
- transport

cooling

shading/ventilation

heat regulation

structural/material adaptation

D.3 Architectural shading & ventilation

Schaduwvoorziening, source: <https://groenblauwenetwerken.nl/measures/bouwkundige-zonwering/>

Evaluation Matrix

cooling

shading/ventilation

[DESCRIPTION] Shading devices, such as shutters, and ventilation structures, such as shafts, can help to block sunlight from entering buildings, and circulate air and remove heat from buildings. // **[PRINCIPLES]** It is important to consider the following principles: use passive design principles (e.g. natural ventilation and solar shading), orient buildings to minimize solar exposure, and select shading devices that are appropriate for the climate and specific needs of the building. // **[CHALLENGES]** Some of the challenges to implementing architectural shading and ventilation systems for adaptation to heat stress include: installation costs, retrofitting existing buildings, which can be challenging and expensive, and lack of awareness.

Co-benefits

Biodiversity	Health	■ ■
Air quality	Education	
Cultural importance & social interaction	Multifunctional use of space	
Water	Tourism/Recreation	
Energy	Resource production	■ ■

Sectoral coalitions

- agriculture/forestry
- aquaculture
- urbanized landscape
- amenities
- industry
- recreation/tourism
- biodiversity
- ecosystems
- water reserves
- energy systems
- mobility infrastructure
- transport

cooling

shading/ventilation

heat regulation

structural/material adaptation

D.4
Thermal insulation

Evaluation Matrix

[DESCRIPTION] Thermal insulation can be used to reduce heat stress in buildings by reducing the amount of heat that enters buildings in the summer and the amount of heat that escapes buildings in the winter (also reducing energy costs). // **[PRINCIPLES]** When designing thermal insulation systems for adaptation to heat stress, it is important to consider the following principles: select the right insulation materials, insulate all parts of the building envelope, and seal air leaks, which can allow heat to enter and escape buildings. // **[CHALLENGES]** Some of the challenges to installing thermal insulation include: installation costs, retrofitting existing buildings, which can be challenging and expensive, and lack of awareness.

Co-benefits

Biodiversity	Health	■ ■
Air quality	Education	
Cultural importance & social interaction	Multifunctional use of space	
Water	Tourism/Recreation	
Energy	Resource production	■ ■

Sectoral coalitions

- | | | | |
|--|----------------------|--|-------------------------|
| | agriculture/forestry | | biodiversity |
| | aquaculture | | ecosystems |
| | urbanized landscape | | water reserves |
| | amenities | | energy systems |
| | industry | | mobility infrastructure |
| | recreation/tourism | | transport |

protection

resistance

heat regulation

structural/material adaptation

D.5
Machine-assisted cooling

Evaluation Matrix

[DESCRIPTION] Air conditioners, fans, and evaporative coolers can help to reduce heat stress through: reducing the temperature of buildings and other spaces, improving air quality, and providing a source of cool water which can be used to drink, bathe, and cool other objects. // **[PRINCIPLES]** It is important to consider the following: size the system appropriately, select the right type of system (based on the specific needs of the space and the availability of resources), and install and maintain the system properly. // **[CHALLENGES]** Some of the challenges include: cost and energy consumption, and, also, maintenance requirements, since such systems require regular maintenance.

Co-benefits

Biodiversity	Health	■
Air quality	Education	
Cultural importance & social interaction	Multifunctional use of space	
Water	Tourism/Recreation	
Energy	Resource production	

Sectoral coalitions

- | | | | |
|--|----------------------|--|-------------------------|
| | agriculture/forestry | | biodiversity |
| | aquaculture | | ecosystems |
| | urbanized landscape | | water reserves |
| | amenities | | energy systems |
| | industry | | mobility infrastructure |
| | recreation/tourism | | transport |

cooling

shading/ventilation

cooling

shading/ventilation